

MASTER THESIS

AN IMAGE-BASED PIPELINE FOR DEFECT
LOCALIZATION IN PHOTONIC INP MULTI-PROJECT
WAFERS

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Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit selbständig und eigenhändig sowie ohne unerlaubte fremde Hilfe und ausschließlich unter Verwendung der aufgeführten Quellen und Hilfsmittel angefertigt habe.

Berlin, den 28.07.2023

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Zusammenfassung

Photonische InP-Wafer werden in begrenzter Stückzahl mittels Lithographie-, Kristallzucht- und Ätzverfahren hergestellt. Die derzeitige Fehlererkennung erfolgt manuell durch menschliche Bediener, doch eine präzise und effiziente Erkennung von Herstellungsfehlern stellt eine offene Herausforderung dar. Herkömmliche Methoden, die auf Schablonenabgleich basieren, sind bei kleinen Prototypen nicht anwendbar. Um dieses Problem anzugehen, bieten wir eine Simulationspipeline basierend auf neuronalen Netzen an, um ein defektfreies Bild zu erzeugen, das einem Foto eines Wafers entspricht. Zusätzlich stellen wir eine Fehlerlokalisierungsmethode vor, die den Unterschied zwischen einem fehlerfreien synthetischen Bild und dem tatsächlichen Foto des hergestellten Wafers analysiert. Wir führen eine empirische Analyse durch, um die Auswirkungen verschiedener Methoden der Computer Vision und des maschinellen Lernens auf die Entwicklung und Leistung dieses Systems zu untersuchen. Unsere Methoden liefern schnelle und zuverlässige Hinweise auf mögliche Defekte mit einstellbarer Empfindlichkeit, was die Effizienz und Zuverlässigkeit des ursprünglichen Defekterkennungsprozesses verbessert.

Abstract

Photonic InP wafers are produced in limited runs through a lithography, crystal growing and etching process. Currently, defect detection is done manually by a human operator. Accurately and efficiently detecting possible manufacturing defects is an open challenge in the field, because traditional template-matching-based methods cannot be used in small scale prototype runs. We provide a neural-net-based simulation pipeline to generate an image analogous to a photo of a wafer, but with no defects. We also provide a defect localization method based on analysing the difference between a defect-free synthetic image and the actual photographic record of the manufactured wafer. We offer an empirical analysis on the effects of several computer vision and machine learning methods on the development and performance of this system. Our methods provide quick and reliable indications of possible defects with adjustable sensitivity, increasing efficiency and reliability of the original defect detection process.

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1 Introduction

Indium-Phosphide (InP) can be used to manufacture photonic devices, offering many theoretical advantages over Silicon-based circuits. Photonic InP multi project wafers (MPW) are produced in limited runs combining designs from many customers on the same wafer for cost-reduction. MPW runs are a complicated process involving lithography, crystal-growth and etching, which often results in “killer defects” — i.e., anomalies that cause a given design to not work as intended, or not work at all. Although the impact is high, the defects are very sparse throughout the wafer’s surface. Currently, for small prototype production runs, a human operator scans the whole wafer surface manually in a microscope to find these defects. This process has a low throughput and is prone to low detection efficiency.

In industrial scale semiconductor manufacturing, wafers contain highly repetitive patterns of the same designs. Automated component level defect detection is traditionally performed by comparing samples with a tested and trusted die and extracting the defect segmentation through template matching. For the experimental photonic InP setting, automatic defect localization is still an open problem due to the absence of a trusted comparison sample for any given design. We will from here onwards refer to this defect-free, trusted die as the *golden standard*.

The work of this thesis is developed between the Department of Artificial Intelligence and the Photonic Components Department of the Fraunhofer Heinrich-Hertz-Institut (HHI) in Berlin, Germany, and deployed at HHI’s foundry. A typical wafer produced at this foundry has a 3-inch diameter, and can contain 20 to 30 different designs. Each individual MPW run has a 6-month lead time, although more than one run are processed in different stages at any given time. Currently at HHI’s foundry, as defect detection has been carried out manually, an automated approach is desired.

We propose a semi-supervised, two step defect-detection pipeline for InP wafers. The backbone of the system is the generation of a synthetic golden standard from the CAD layout files and the photo of a potentially defective wafer. A U-Net – a fully convolutional neural network initially designed for semantic segmentation – is trained with the CAD templates as input and a quantized photo of the respective wafer is used as a target. The neural network quickly learns a defect-free representation of the wafer due to the strong correlation of the structures in the CAD data with the realized components. We show that the models can also learn to hallucinate defects if trained on very high defect densities, but that typical defect densities in this use-case do not affect simulation robustness. We then computationally compare the photo of an actual wafer with this generated golden standard, and leverage the difference between both to detect and localize the defects at the pixel level. We conduct experiments on real data and synthetic data to explore the method’s accuracy and robustness, both in golden standard simulation and in defect detection. An overview of the proposed system is presented in Figure 1.1.

The remaining of this work is organized as follows:

- In Chapter 2 we cover the current literature on the main topics approached by this work: the MPW setting for manufacturing of InP wafers, the current methods used for defect detection in the semiconductor industry, and how image-based defect detection is applied to several industries and application domains. We also cover generative machine learning models that use the U-Net architecture, some current and established views in object, defect and anomaly detection, and a brief discussion on the definitions of different supervision levels in those domains.
- Chapter 3 reviews the quality metrics used in this work for evaluating simulation quality, defect detection performance and optimization objectives. We also discuss motivations and

implications of each according to our use-case scenario.

- Chapter 4 is dedicated to present the data used in this work and the related methods. We describe a data-processing pipeline composed of several software components, preparing the raw data into the system's input format. We also depict the two kinds of synthetic data we use along this work.
- In Chapter 5 we present the techniques used to simulate a defect-free wafer image. We demonstrate the methods for different defect densities and evaluate the simulation results in terms of several quality metrics. We also present an input filtering method to speed-up the training process.
- We present the actual defect detection step in Chapter 6, with experiments to showcase the applicability and limits of robustness of our methods.
- Chapter 7 is dedicated to comment on our findings and discuss the applicability and evaluation of defect detection methods on real world data, where ground-truth data may be insufficient or of low-quality.
- We conclude in Chapter 8 with a summary of our main contributions and suggestions on future research directions.

The full dataset with actual wafer designs is not made available as it contains third-party intellectual property, but all images shown in this work come from pre-approved sections of the original dataset.

Figure 1.1 The complete pipeline of the proposed methodology. We encapsulate the raw data in a common format as our dataset (1), and apply some pre-processing steps (2) before feeding it to the simulation network (3). The CAD layers for a patch are used as input for the simulation and the discretized wafer’s photo as training target, characterizing this step as supervised. The photo is later also used for comparison with the predicted patch (4). The defect detection (5) itself is unsupervised, and we evaluate the results (6) comparing to labeled data and to synthetic datasets. The samples showed in the diagram all correspond to the same patch. The wafer depicted in this example has 24 CAD layers, more than depicted. We present this method as *semi-supervised* because the supervised step uses data generated intrinsically in the manufacturing process.

2 Background and Related Work

In this work, we make use of well established concepts from computer vision and machine learning research applied to quality control in InP photonic wafer manufacturing. Below we introduce and discuss some fundamental knowledge of each of those areas. Some more specific details will be also introduced where required in further chapters, as the methodology is explained in detail.

2.1 Automatic visual inspection of semiconductors

Photonic wafers are manufactured through a complex combination of epitaxial crystal growth [41], etching and lithography processes, either on silicon or indium phosphate (InP) substrates. The development of InP-based wafers is desirable, because it allows for the integration of lasers and optical amplifiers, smaller scales and operation in higher frequency [46]. InP photonic integration is, however, more expensive and prone to defects, and generally less developed than silicon-based integration. Kish et al. [39] indicate that integration in photonics follows the technological development of silicon-based electronics with a 20-year offset. For example, a “killer random defect density” $< 1 \text{ cm}^{-2}$ is the current state of the art in InP photonics, but was achieved for silicon-based electronics as early as 1990. They divide the main current manufacturability challenges in (a) manufacturing yield, **(b) killer defect density** and (c) performance yield. In this work, we focus on (b), but we do not differentiate between “killer” and “cosmetic” defects [13].

In semiconductor production we should have very low false alarm tolerance rates [15]. Manual inspection is time consuming and prone to performance decrease due to operator fatigue. Cost of labour and limited hours of human operators is also a factor [31]. Generally in automated approaches, the goal is to rival human performance without the pitfalls mentioned [49]. It is reported that the accuracy of manual classification would be typically around 60% to 80% in manufacturing lines, and that the human operator is the limiting factor for the performance of a neural network-based semi-automatic *human-in-the-loop* system [13]. Therefore, a fully automatic inspection approach is very desirable in the industry.

It is worth mentioning that some methods also use non-image data, relying instead on the measurement of some proxy process variable. For example, the temperature can be used to model warpage [26], and pressure, reflected emissions, and other quantities during the several steps of the process are used for quality control as well [55]. A silicon wafer containing several repeated chips can also be tested for functionality. This generates a “bin map”, showing where the defective chips are as a coarser version of the wafer itself. Some methods rely on this wafer bin map (WBM) instead of an optical image [37], for which machine vision methods still apply. These methods require access to the process and possibly expensive setups.

Image-based approaches for semiconductors have been proposed since a long time [4], due to low cost, flexibility and the possibility to integrate them into human-operated review stations. Image-based methods are also non-invasive [75].

It is also important to acknowledge how flexible image-based methods are in its cross domain functionality: image-based defect detection methods are also applied to defect detection in Li-Ion batteries [2], semantic segmentation for defect detection in wood [20], detection of rust defects in steel bridges [42], detection of electrical commutator cracks [69], defect detection in textile fabric [28] and several works on steel sheets [53, 21, 24]. Most of these works are applied in scenes with location invariant structure, such as recurring patterns and textures, such as the samples in Figure 2.1 show. It could be argued that on recurring patterns simple methods can be used with good results, such as the Gabor filter [17], but the use of supervised learning defect recognition schemes dominates the field, showing better overall performance [6]. In comparison, electronic circuits are considered

Figure 2.1 Examples of defective image-samples in other domains of application, and their sources: (a) Li-Ion batteries [2], (b) knot on wood [20], (c) hot-rolled steel sheets [24], (d) DC motor commutator cracks [69], (e) solar panels [44], (f) textile fabric [28], (g) and (h) wafer [78].

more “complicated images” [71].

It is possible to separate the visual inspection problem in *localization* and *classification* of defects. Localization methods aim to find exactly where in the image a defect occurs, while a general classification method should predict which type of defect occurs in a patch, not necessarily with regards for location. Those two scenarios are not mutually exclusive and it is generally even desirable to have a method that performs both localization and classification. In fact, sometimes one occurs as a side effect of the other [57]. This work deals with localization, but a binary classification defect/no-defect is attained as well.

In traditional industrial silicon-based semiconductor manufacturing, the automatic defect *localization* problem is solved in high-volume manufacturing trivially. In fact, most of the works involving deep learning in semiconductor defect detection take the localization for granted, using datasets where defective patches were pre-selected from the original raw data. Those works focus instead on patch-wise defect classification [9]. Due to the high volume repetition and regular grid like structure, a defect-free golden standard die can be used as a reference for comparison [15, 31]. Chin and Harlow [12] call this kind of comparison *differential scanning*, by scanning two adjacent designs and comparing them, already in 1982. Many template matching methods were developed for this purpose since the 80s [71]. Earlier methods also focus on specific parts of the wafer, to make the problem more tractable [78].

According to the survey by Huang and Pan [31], image-based inspection systems in the semiconductor industry traditionally rely on simple subtraction or template matching. Several improvements can be made for robustness, such as using frequency transforms to make the detection shift- and rotation-invariant. Many methods also use several kinds of approaches, mentioned in literature as “hybrid methods”. They mention that the same kinds of image based methods are used for several products, such as wafers, TFT display and LEDs, each with their own particularities.

For all of those, the output is a score map, such as the ones in Figure 2.2. Huang and Pan [31] also mention that processing time is an important bottleneck. This is not a consideration in our setting, as the lead time for MPW runs is around 6 months, and any computation for the methods presented can be done in the order of hours, at most.

Figure 2.2 Visualizations of the “score maps” generated by different approaches in the literature. In the right of each subfigure we can see the score map generated for the corresponding patch in the left.

There is interestingly also a body of related work for defect detection in textiles, where the main difference from our domain is that the textures are more or less translation invariant, and where the main similarities are the same drawbacks caused by human visual inspection. Methods can therefore isolate the reoccurring pattern and use some similarity metric over this golden sample [51, 56].

2.2 Image generation using U-Nets

The InP wafers for which this work applies are prototypes, and manufacturing happens in much lower scale than in industrial silicon-based applications. In fact, the foundry at HHI manufactures multi project wafers (MPW), which allow for chips from different designers to be manufactured in the same wafer. The foundry provides a standardized library of “basic building blocks” (optical amplifiers, phase shifters...), which can be combined to realize multiple intricate designs. The total production cost is shared by multiple customers, viabilizing small scale experimental production [67, 66]. Liehr et al. [46] note that a current MPW run takes around 6 months to be manufactured. The variety of designs limits the way in which differential scanning and template matching could work, as in general MPW runs have no golden standard to compare against. With current generative machine learning (ML) models we aim at generating a synthetic golden standard.

The use of ML is widespread for supervised defect classification in current literature. Convolutional neural networks (CNN) are the most common kind of architecture used to classify samples [10, 37, 33, 11]. These methods provide a classification label for a whole defective patch, reflecting a trend in this field of research. Wang et al. [74] provide a supervised defect detection method for wafers at the bounding box level. To the best of our knowledge there are no works using CNNs to generate a wafer’s golden standard.

The backbone of our system uses an U-Net. Ronneberger et al. [62] developed the U-Net for semantic segmentation in black and white histological images. It has an encoder-decoder architecture with skip connections between layers of the same scale. The skip connections could act in making the loss landscape smoother and easier to train [43]. The original layout of the U-Net architecture is shown at Figure 2.3. Our implementation has one extra input dimension.

Figure 2.3 The original U-Net architecture, a convolutional encoder-decoder with skip connections. Image taken from the work of Ronneberger et al. [62].

Many modifications were made in further work by other authors, for applications across diverse fields. A modified U-Net is used to generate/inpaint background in a scene [70], for generating photos from LiDAR data (with MSE loss) [36], or for image superresolution [29]. Liang et al. [45] used a U-Net with skip connections only in the lower levels, to aid in segmentation of concealed objects in THz imagery. They argue that the low level features from the higher resolution layers have too much information about background and edges, leading to too many false positives in the segmentation masks.

Some methods use a similar approach that we use, of generating realistic images from semantic segmentation labels. Pan et al. [59] generate videos from semantic segmentation maps applied to cityscapes and to human movement. Isola et al. [34] use a U-Net as a generator for a conditional generative adversarial network (cGAN), and mention that the skip connections keep input and output structures aligned — a desirable property in our setting. They also show how the presence of skip connections generates sharper results. Wang et al. [73] also use a cGAN on semantic segmentation labels, to manipulate the appearance of real datasets. Results in both works are evaluated both empirically by humans, and by testing if models pre-trained with the original images work out-of-the-box with the generic images.

Some methods focus on adding synthetic defects to clean samples, in order to augment the training data. Boikov et al. [7] use a U-Net for supervised defect segmentation in steel samples. Similarly to us, though, they create parametric shaders to mimic defects, and then train a U-Net with supervision on this data. In the domain of defect detection in semiconductor samples, Chen

et al. [9] also adds synthetic defects to real samples, and train an YOLOv3 model [60] on this augmented set. They train only on patches containing defects, and only in the background of the wafer.

Unsupervised generative methods are also popular for anomaly detection in hyperspectral aerial imagery. Bati et al. [3] encode and decode a patch with an autoencoder, and anomalies should yield a greater reconstruction error. Arisoy et al. [1] build upon this by using an adversarial autoencoder, reconstruction error compared with the input patch. Hyperspectral imagery may contain complex backgrounds, which make learning the negative samples harder. Guo et al. [22] overcome this with synthetic data for training and evaluation.

Hu et al. [28] adopt an approach similar to ours for defect detection in textiles, by generating a synthetic defect free fabric sample using a convolutional neural net. A modified GAN trained on defect-free samples generates from feature space a defect-free patch of fabric. Their generator network is also an encoder-decoder, but without skip connections. A detector is then trained on photos and simulations. Contrary to us, they use datasets with relatively balanced representations of each class of defects. Since fabric is mostly a recurring pattern, a simulated patch does not have alignment issues, as mentioned before. An “inverter” network takes a photo to the feature space, thus removing defects. They use a manually annotated dataset with tight segmentation labels. A separate model is trained for each kind of fabric. Their results are shown in Figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4 Hu et al. [28] detect defects in (a) a fabric sample by (b) generating a synthetic golden standard and (c) computing a differential score map.

2.3 The challenges towards unsupervised object detection

A key consideration in the setting of object detection is the sparsity of positive samples [64, 48, 77]. Defect detection (also anomaly detection) can be seen as a special case of object detection, where the occurrence of objects is even more sparse [6]. In this work, we will refer to these terms interchangeably. Since labeling segmentation datasets is time-consuming and human resources tend to be expensive, unsupervised and self- or semi-supervised approaches are desirable [8]. Even if there is some evidence that for simpler textures it is possible to train a supervised semantic segmentation model for surface defect detection on a very small dataset of positive samples [69], it is desirable to try to minimize the amount of labeled data and generalize the behaviour for complex cases too.

The definition of the term *unsupervised* depends sometimes on the exact application and varies from work to work, but it is generally understood as a framework in which no labeled ground-truth data is needed. The development of a method completely without ground-truth data is impossible,

as this data is needed at least for evaluating the performance of the models. In reality, approaches fall in a spectrum of how much labeled data they use and in which coarseness. Many works devise interesting techniques to leverage whatever data is available, and some so-called unsupervised methods actually rely on a pre-trained detector back bone, trained with supervision on a distinct but related task. This is referred to as “base training”. The model is then fine-tuned and evaluated on base data and novel data for the application at hand [30]. Some methods add synthetic anomalies to the training data as an augmentation strategy [7]. Some works claim to be unsupervised, but are trained on images known to be defect-free [72, 52]. They are unsupervised in the sense that defect data is not present in training. In our use-case, defective data is present in the dataset but not labeled, so at first view indistinguishable from good data.

In a compromise between the lack of detailed labeled ground truth data for full supervision and the overall inherent difficulty in developing a truly unsupervised method, lies the field of *weakly supervised object detection* (WSOD) [77]. In WSOD, coarse labels are used for a finer-grained task, and many kinds of data augmentation are usually used, aiming to get good results while allowing for quicker, cheaper and less precise labelling. An example of WSOD is performing localization and semantic segmentation through image-level labels [57]. More recently, works using explainability are also augmenting the coarseness of classification to the pixel-wise semantic segmentation direction [?]. In the development of WSOD methods, classic ML models, such as SVMs with hand crafted features, were used extensively. They were superseded by pre-trained deep learning models and eventually by dedicated WSOD models. This approach is used currently in several applications, such as video understanding, art images, medical images, and quite extensively on aerial imagery [77, 23].

Labeled data is important for automatic supervised training, but may not be necessary for a human/expert who looks at the data and has the same task. In fact, as mentioned above, some works actually hire people to evaluate generative models [34, 73]. Before 2014 – when the deep learning-based approaches took the center stage –, state-of-the-art saliency detection methods were mostly hand-crafted [81, 49]. In applications, it is common to balance automatic and hand-crafted methods in the same pipeline [6]. Most methods still rely in the general approach of a sliding window over some feature map, with some metric which may or may not require supervision.

Also expanding from Chou et al. [13] we can say that it is impossible to evaluate models after deployment, as there is no ground-truth at this point, as stated by Kohlberger et al. [40]. There is work in the sense of evaluating unlabeled data [40, 76]. Kohlberger et al. [40] train a model for error estimation with ground truth data and use this model to evaluate other models, instead of ground-truth data. A similar approach is used to develop the *learned perceptual index for patch similarity* (LPIPS) [80], which train a neural net for perceptual similarity using human feedback as supervision data.

The field of *unsupervised* defect detection is somewhat new and an open area of research [30]. Mujeeb et al. [52] use RMSE as a similarity score to evaluate patches of steel sheets in feature space. Volkau et al. [72] applies a similar approach for PCBs, using a pre-trained CNN, and set a separation threshold manually. Both works provide patch-wise scores, and the target image is divided in a grid. The method provides then a score map that is coarser/lower resolution than the image.

For more sophisticated use-cases, it is interesting to detect several different objects in the same image – i.e. each instance of an object has to be detected. Each detected object is usually contained in a bounding box, and the pixels inside it may not necessarily be part of the object. Most modern supervised object detection frameworks consist of region proposal networks and bounding box regressors [81]. In this work, we also get bounding boxes, but simply by extracting the contours of the thresholded score map.

3 Review of evaluation metrics

In this work, we frame the generation of an artificial golden standard wafer as a semantic segmentation problem, and train a model accordingly. We quantize RGB photos of a photonic wafer in a discrete palette of colors, which are used by the model as classification classes. We train a neural network to minimize the difference between the network’s output and the reference photo. We then again measure the differences between this golden standard to the photo, in order to obtain a numerical indication of possible defects’ location. Finally, we need to evaluate whether the trained models perform well on the tasks of simulation and defect detection.

There are many evaluation metrics described in literature for all of the distinct tasks we aim to achieve. We need to use a loss function for training the neural network, perceptual similarity metrics to evaluate the simulation quality and binary classification metrics to evaluate defect detections and bounding box generation.

3.1 Loss functions, distances and similarity metrics

A semantic segmentation neural network model is a pixel-wise classification model for k classes. The model outputs raw prediction scores $s_s(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^k$ for each pixel with (x, y) coordinates and classes $c \in [1..k]$. Such a model is trained using a loss function, a similarity metric between the output and some ground truth. The main objective in training is to optimize this similarity, usually by gradient descent. Therefore a loss function has to be implemented in a differentiable way. There are several types of loss functions used in semantic segmentation, including distribution-based and region-based functions [35]. Some loss functions accept the raw prediction scores s_s and a quantized target t_q as input. We train our models with a pixel-wise categorical cross entropy with k colors, a distribution-based loss function described by

$$CE(s_s, t_q) = -\log \frac{\exp(s_s(t_q))}{\sum_{c=1}^k \exp(s_s(c))} \quad (1)$$

and we aim to minimize it. The computed pixel-wise loss can be averaged over all pixels in a batch, obtaining a scalar metric to be optimized during training. Loss functions can also be used simply as a similarity metric which compares the raw prediction scores with the quantized target. We evaluate our simulations in chapters 5 and 6 with cross-entropy, and also use the Dice Loss [68], region based and modified from the Sorensen-Dice coefficient, and the focal loss [48], created specifically for unbalanced datasets in semantic segmentation.

The class predicted by the model is the highest scoring class for a given pixel, given by

$$p_q(x, y) = \underset{k}{\operatorname{argmax}} s_s(x, y), \quad (2)$$

which in our setting we will treat as the quantized golden standard, in the same space and with the same dimensions as the quantized photo. We are also interested in evaluating our simulation models in this space, computing for example the accuracy of our estimator – i.e. how much of the predicted pixels are of the correct class. In particular, since our color palette contains many similar colors and the photo has considerable noise, we would like to be lenient in this evaluation and accept as a correct prediction pixels that were estimated to be of a neighbouring color in the color palette. We implement a k -off accuracy measure which takes the quantized prediction p_q and target t_q as inputs and computes the simulation accuracy, but considering pixels predicted in the range $[t_q - k .. t_q + k]$ as correct. The k -off accuracy is given by

$$A_k(p_q, t_q) = \frac{|\sum_{-k}^k (L_k \cap t_q)|}{|t_q|} \quad (3)$$

with

$$L_k = \begin{cases} p_q + k - k_{max}, & \text{if } p_q + k > k_{max}, \\ p_q + k + k_{max}, & \text{if } p_q + k < 1, \\ p_q + k, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where k_{max} is the number of colors, to go around the color palette when indexes overflow. We extend the 1-off accuracy to k -off from Eidinger et al. [16], which use a similar concept for a lenient metric in age prediction. We aim to get the highest k -off accuracy possible in our trained models. Notice that this measure has to be used with an ordered and cyclic colorspace, such that neighbouring colors are semantically similar and that the indexes $c = 1$ and $c = k_{max}$ also contain similar colors. Such a colorspace will be introduced in more detail in Chapter 4.

We also evaluate our models with perceptual similarity metrics applied to RGB images, with p_{RGB} and t_{RGB} as inputs. They intend to capture similarity in human-perception terms. We can use L1 and L2-norms, which are not directly perceptual similarity metrics but are often used as such. There is evidence that L1 loss measures perceptual similarity for humans better than L2 [65]. The peak signal to noise ratio (PSNR) originated in the domain of signal processing and image transmission, and is usually the mean square error between an image and its reconstruction in dB, a logarithmic scale. For RGB images, it is the sum of the MSE of each channel and normalized after. It is a valid quality assessment index when the images compared have the same content, but doesn't model human perception very well [32]. The structural similarity index measure (SSIM) is a widely used metric, which also takes into account contextual information from windows in an image. PSNR and SSIM are prevalent and well studied [27]. More recently, works have shown that PSNR might be unsuitable for segmentation [19] and SSIM shows several deficiencies as a metric in general [54]. We use them as references. Haar wavelet-based perceptual similarity index (HaarPSI) developed by Reisenhofer et al. [61]. Its implementation is differentiable, provides efficient computation and shows a higher correlation to human opinion than the metrics mentioned above. The learned perceptual patch similarity index (LPIPS) is part of a recent shift in trying to model human perception through neural networks [80]. It is a neural network trained on human opinion of perceptual similarity, and has shown to translate well to other domains. Different metrics applied in the same task might generate contradicting results [79]. We keep our metric selection ample in order to leverage as much information as possible from the values computed. In further sections, we indicate the metrics for which we desire a higher score by the symbol of an arrow pointing up (\uparrow). For metrics such as distances and loss functions, we aim at obtaining a lower score, and indicate accordingly (\downarrow).

3.2 Binary classification

After we apply some similarity metric to a predicted golden standard and the corresponding target image, we obtain a scalar similarity score $s_d(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}$. For all pixels in (x, y) coordinates, we call this s_d , the defect detection score map. Binary defect classification from a score map of this kind is achieved by finding a binarization threshold T which separates the image in positive samples (the defects) and negative samples (no defect), such as in

$$p_b(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } s_d(x, y) > T, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

In most applications, the data in the score map is not linearly separable and there is no single value for T which would generate a perfectly accurate detection. Misclassified samples are unavoi-

able, and the main design goal for methods developed for this task is to define which tolerance of errors is acceptable for a given use-case, and set a corresponding binarization threshold. Correctly identified positive samples are called “true positives” (TP), and correctly identified negative samples are “true negatives” (TN). Misclassified samples are, accordingly, “false positives” (FP) and “false negatives” (FN). The tolerance for each kind of misclassified samples varies by application, and there will always be a trade-off relationship among the 4 types of classification described. In defect detection there is a false tolerance to FN detections, as any defect that goes unnoticed by the quality control might generate big financial impact in the manufacturing setting. In other words, the cost associated with FP predictions is lower, and a higher tolerance for this kind of prediction is accepted.

Many quantities are derived from the ratio between these types of classification. We focus on the following: A classifier’s precision (positive predictive value, PPV) is the rate of detections that are true positives,

$$PPV = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}. \quad (6)$$

The sensitivity, recall or true positive rate (TPR) is the rate of true positives in all the data classified as positive, given by

$$TPR = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}. \quad (7)$$

The specificity, or false positive rate (FPR) is the rate of incorrectly classified negative samples for the data that is actually negative, defined as

$$FPR = \frac{FP}{FP + TN}. \quad (8)$$

Two useful tools that emerge from the analysis of binary classification are the “receiver-operator characteristic” (ROC) plot and the “precision-recall” curve.

The ROC shows the trade-off between sensitivity and specificity, and is plotting by computing pairs of TPR and FPR for different threshold values. The area under this plot (AUROC) is a single scalar statistic that is many times used to summarize the classification performance when using this kind of plot. The AUROC exists in the $[0, 1]$ interval, and any classifier with AUROC ≥ 0.5 is said to perform better than a random classifier.

The trade-off between precision (PPV) and recall (TPR) generated for different thresholds can be shown in the Precision-Recall plot. We can also use the area under this plot as a single statistic to summarize a classifier’s performance. The area under the Precision-Recall curve can be approximated by the “average precision” (AP), given by

$$AP = \sum_n (R_n - R_{n-1})P_n, \quad (9)$$

where P_n and R_n are the precision and recall at the n -th threshold. It is the weighted mean of precisions at each threshold point. This area can also be computed by trapezoidal interpolation.

While the chance baseline for the ROC plot is fixed at 0.5, the baseline for a random classifier in a Precision-Recall plot depends on the data imbalance present in the dataset. It is the ratio of positive samples in the whole data, and therefore varies from dataset to dataset. For example, for 20% positive labeled samples in a dataset, the chance of randomly choosing one is 2/10, or 20%. Data imbalance is a very important consideration to be made when choosing a way to display binary classification results. Saito and Rehmsmeier [63] argue that the Precision-Recall curve should be used when there are imbalanced datasets. It was also shown that a classifier dominates in ROC space if and only if it also dominates in the Precision-Recall curve [14]. We generate both plots for our pixel-wise evaluation of defect detection in Chapter 6.

3.3 Bounding box-based evaluation

Pixel-wise evaluation for object detection can incur in high error when the segmentation labels differ slightly in alignment or coverage. One proposed solution in the literature is to move to instance-based metrics, which consider whether a certain object was detected or not, without such a regard for tight labels. Most object detection frameworks in current literature in fact consist of region proposal networks and bounding box regressors [81]. Their aim is to find a general contour around individual instances of objects instead of relying in pixel-wise classification and semantic segmentation. Evaluation metrics in this context are expanded from the pixel-wise binary classification task, based mostly on the concept of precision, since there are no negative samples. A very important concept introduced for bounding-box based settings is the “intersection over union” metric (IoU), also known as the Jaccard index and given by

$$J(A, B) = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|}, \quad (10)$$

being A and B the set of pixels in two bounding boxes. As bounding boxes span more than one pixel and the detection for several different objects might intersect, the IoU can be used to indicate whether some predicted bounding box should be evaluated or not. If two bounding boxes are disjoint, $\text{IoU} = 0$, and $\text{IoU} = 1$ if they match perfectly. In usual literature bounding boxes can be discarded if they don’t overlap by more than 50% with the ground truth label [58].

One of the most used sets of evaluation metrics for bounding box-based object detection is the one proposed by the “COCO” challenge [47]. Among other metrics, they analyse the average precision for IoUs bigger than 50% and 75%. They also evaluate object detection models with the mean average precision (mAP), which is the mean of the APs for IoUs between 50% and 95%, at 0.05 increments. The average precision at 50% IoU is also the main metric for the Pascal VOC challenge [18].

The bounding box-based metrics mentioned are used for general object detection. The setting of defect detection differs in requirements, mostly because of the sparsity of positive samples. There is also not such an emphasis in bounding box exactness, but in correct detections [74].

4 Data

The data used in this work is supplied by the foundry at Fraunhofer HHI. Most of the designs are intellectual property from HHI’s customers, and are therefore non-publishable. It is a trend in this field that data is not publicly available, and replicating existing results is often not realistic. There are datasets for industrial defect segmentation, such as Bergmann et al. [5], which are suitable for domain transfer and provide well-labeled examples of both good and defective instances. It presents whole objects, mimicking scenarios that can be found in current industrial applications. Wang et al. [74] mention the “WDD” dataset, which the authors created themselves, but is not available. To our knowledge, there are no publicly available datasets that relate the building plans of integrated circuits to images of the final product. All images shown here are for a publishable portion of our wafer.

From the foundry, we have access to the CAD layouts and photos of a manufactured multi project wafer. We implemented the software pipeline shown in Figure 4.1 to process this data, and store photos, CAD layout, defect labels, simulations and defect detection score maps in a stack of image-like data structures – i.e. all of the same size and spatially aligned, such as shown in Figure 4.2. The processing pipeline aims to represent the data in a way that directly allows the application of image-based methods. Apart from the few steps that require user input, the data

Figure 4.1 Data generation pipeline. The set of CAD layout files and the photo of the wafer are obtained from the foundry. The CAD layouts have to be converted into bitmaps and aligned to the photo (1). A human operator has to choose manually the keypoints for alignment. We generate labeled defect data with a manual graphic annotation tool (2). The labeled data, the CAD layouts and the RGB photo are stored by our so called “dataset generator” (3) in a HDF5 file. The dataset generator also quantizes the photo and finds a reduced color palette for it. From there, the data is fed to the rest of the pipeline (4), as shown in Figure 1.1. Alternatively, synthetic data can be used. The toy data generator creates image files mimicking the real data (5), which are then quantized and encapsulated in an HDF5 file by the dataset generator as well. In this work we will refer to this file containing the data for a wafer as a “dataset”. Each of the blue rectangles in the diagram is a different software module implemented.

*The bitmap generator and the engine of the toy data generator are not direct contributions of this work and had been implemented previously.

processing pipeline can be automated. Each data type and pre-processing step will be discussed further below in this chapter.

We only have labelled data for one chip in the wafer, and those labels are usually in the bounding box format, covering more irrelevant pixels than defect pixels. To aid in the evaluation of our methods we also generate a parametric toy dataset and augment the original data with synthetic defects. In this way we have control over defect density and pixel-wise perfect defect labels in the data. The toy data generator is also published, so some results in this work can be replicated.

4.1 Photos

The photos of a wafer are used as a training target for the simulation neural network. The wafers are photographed through a microscope after manufacturing. As the microscope’s field of view doesn’t fit the whole wafer, it is photographed in several smaller patches. The patches are then stitched in a high-resolution panorama. The stitching is done automatically by tools provided by the microscope manufacturer. The 50-fold magnification used results in approximately 2,600 pixels/cm, or 3.8 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$. Exact figures vary slightly from wafer to wafer, due to the manual positioning of the wafers in the image acquisition system. A whole wafer has a diameter of 3 inches and the

Figure 4.2 Visual representation of the several kinds of data associated with one wafer. Labels are stored as a binary map in $\{-1, 1\}$, here overlaid over the photo for easier visualization. The defects are usually smaller than the corresponding labels, which also mark many non-defective pixels. Last image is colored with a different color for each combination of stacked CAD layers. The layers are actually binary image images which usually overlap each other – see Figure 4.8(a).

image has a resolution of around $20,000 \times 20,000$ pixels.

The images are sourced originally in RGB format. To fit the data to the semantic segmentation model and clean the data from excessive noise, we discretize the photos to 64 colors before using them as targets for training the model.

Digital images are usually represented as rectangles, but wafers are round. Our images have a big portion in the corners not related to the wafer, but we ignore them for the purposes of this work. The CAD layer which masks the out-of-wafer area can be seen in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3 Mask of the outside area of the wafer used in this work. The darker shaded areas in the image are discarded in our work, and represents 29.6% of the whole image. This proportion varies from wafer to wafer, due to the manual positioning in the image acquisition system.

4.1.1 Quantization and ordering

We use semantic segmentation models, which require a discrete target space. The wafers analysed in this work are composed of a small set of materials, which are represented in the photo by a limited amount of colors. The 8-bit, 3-channel RGB space used in this work spans 256^3 possible colors. As seen in the Figure 4.4(a), our colours of interest occupy a very limited subset of this

(a) 20,000 pixel samples in the RGB cube, color-coded to the RGB coordinates.

(b) 64-color cyclic palette.

Figure 4.4 The colorspace typically occupied by a wafer. (a) Color expression of 20,000 sample pixels from a wafer, shown in the RGB cube. It is easy to see how the color expression of a wafer photo is very limited. This suggests that a reduction in colorspace may be of interest. (b) Ordered color palette for the wafer analysed in this work. The k -means clustering algorithm used to quantize the colorspace has the tendency to generate clusters of similar size, so we can see how over-represented colors occupy a bigger portion of the palette.

RGB space. To both reduce the problem in a more tractable sub-space and to adapt the data to be used with the U-Net, we quantize it in fewer colors.

We use the k -means clustering algorithm for quantizing the colorspace, and empirically conclude that 64 colors are enough to represent the wafers. We fit the algorithm to 20,000 pixels sampled at random from the whole wafer. In Figure 4.5 one can see the results of quantizations with different amounts of colors. As we actually want to see the correct segmentation masks for a given *material* in the end, and there are limited materials, we only need limited colors.

Moreover, it is not accurate to describe our setting as purely a semantic segmentation problem, as we don't have exactly one correct class for each pixel. We would like to be lenient in the evaluation of the simulation and consider also colors that are not identical but similar to the one in the target pixel, as we know the original photo is affected by considerable noise. We order our palette to be able to evaluate neighbouring colors of the predicted one. To order the palette, we take the 64 cluster centroids from the quantization step, each an RGB value, and apply a solver for the traveling salesman problem, treating each centroid as a node in the graph and finding the path that connects all colors with the smallest accumulated node-to-node distance. For the wafer used in this work, this approach results in the palette shown in Figure 4.4(b). This is an *ordered* and *cyclic* palette.

At the time of writing this work, we have one different palette per wafer series – i.e. different instances of the same wafer have the same color palette. That is necessary for the correct decoding and evaluation of the simulation results.

Figure 4.5 A patch of a RGB wafer photo and the reconstructed versions with the respective number of colors used and the attained SSIM. We notice that, although in some cases a reduced amount of colors may provide a high structural similarity measure, discretization in 64 classes/colors provides images almost indistinguishable from those in the RGB space, both perceptually and in terms of SSIM. The relative high similarity for the 4-color sample is considered an anomaly and not guaranteed to generalize well to other patches, as it is clear to see how some important hues are missing from the palette.

4.2 CAD Layout Data

The CAD data used in the foundry’s process is originally stored in the “Graphic Design System II” (GDSII, also referred here as GDS) format, the industry standard format for data exchange in integrated circuit manufacturing. We convert the GDSII files to binary image layers and apply a homography transformation so they get aligned over the photo.

The GDS binary files are first converted to 24 binary bitmap files with available tools¹. The actual GDSII files contain more layers, but some are merged so each transformed CAD image layer corresponds to one manufacturing step, and we also add a layer masking inside and outside of the wafer (Figure 4.3).

The raw CAD data contains descriptions of the geometric structures in each layer, but not necessarily any scale correspondence with the photo, so the generated bitmaps need to be transformed to fit over the photo. We use a tool to manually select corresponding keypoint pairs between the photo and the GDS bitmaps, from which a homography transformation is then computed. There is a strong requirement for alignment between the defective sample and the golden standard for defect detection [25], and in semantic segmentation models learned output structures are spatially aligned to the same structures in input. Therefore, the keypoints have to be chosen with care.

4.3 Labeled defect data

We need ground-truth defect labels to evaluate the defect detection performance. To gather those labels, we developed a decentralized annotation tool, in which a server hosts the wafer’s photo and sends a patch of it to a client GUI application (shown in Figure 4.6). The patch can be either selected randomly by the server application or manually by the user. The user then draws the contour for the visible defects and assigns them a class. This data is then sent back to the server for integration into the dataset. Due to the server-client architecture, the tool can be used to scale data collection to multiple clients.

¹The bitmap generator tool is not a direct contribution from this work. The software implementation of the process described in this session was available as a result of previous work. We nonetheless describe the data pre-processing for completeness.

Figure 4.6 An early version of the web client’s GUI of the developed labeling tool. The main window shows a patch of the wafer, and its location in the wafer is indicated by the rectangle in the minimap. In the minimap region we can also observe the round shape of a wafer. The menu in the right panel lets the user select which drawing tool will be used and which kind of defect will be marked.

The framework developed with this labeling tool comes also with a framework to edit the labels and eventually transform them into binary masks for integration into the regular dataset, such as the one showed in Figure 4.2. The data can also be used for training classification models, as labels assign classes to the defects.

The annotation tool has also a set of functions to transform labels. For smaller memory footprint, they are compressed in a `uint16` unsigned 16-bit integer number, bit encoded, where each pixel p_{xy} in the label map has the value

$$p_{xy} = \sum_{k=0}^{15} l_k 2^k, \quad (11)$$

where k is the label for a defect class, and

$$l_k = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if there is a defect of class } k, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

This format allows for the decoding of a label of class k to be a simple bitwise AND boolean operation with 2^k . This work doesn’t focus on defect classification, so the labels used for evaluating defect detection are binary, converted from the bit-encoded representation in Equation (12) by

$$l_d = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{where } p_{xy} > 0, \\ -1, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

The defect class can still be taken into account in further work, as it is stored in the dataset.

For this work, we had one person labelling the wafer. Due to the labour intensive nature of the process, we have labeled data only for the publishable design in the wafer. This chip corresponds to 1.6% of the wafer surface. Some labels are tight around the defect, and some have other shapes, but typically they are similar to the one shown in Figure 4.2: square regions containing a defect, but also containing several surrounding pixels which do not correspond to the defects. Pixel-wise metrics will perform poorly due to too many false positives in the labeled data.

The experiments described in this work use the full wafer for training and evaluating the simulator, but only the fully-labeled section for evaluating defect detection on real data.

4.4 Toy data

We also use a procedurally generated dataset to provide a more controlled environment to test our methods. We will call this set *toy data* in the remainder of this work. The toy data generator allows us to parametrize defect density for some kinds of defects. We assume we can generalize most of the conclusions from models trained on toy data to real data. The toy dataset is also published in the repository mentioned in the first chapter².

The toy data follows the rough characteristics of the real data, but with less CAD layers and without a round border, so the whole area of the image is composed of a wafer. It also implements “contextual structures”, i.e. structures described in a pixel in the CAD layers and spanning a region in the photo. In Figure 4.7 we show such a structure highlighted.

Figure 4.7 The toy data also incorporates the contextual dependence from CAD to photo. In the example pictured here, we can see that the color of the component changes near its border. This is not expressly indicated in the CAD layer in the left. For a model to learn such structures, it has to take into account the neighbouring pixels of a region. All other CAD layers for this patch have no information.

First, the artificial CAD layers are generated. Layers contain either random polygons, horizontal text or traces generated by a maze-generating algorithm. In Figure 4.8 one can see how the toy CAD data in Figure 4.8(b) looks similar to the actual data in Figure 4.8(a). It is important to note that the toy datasets are square, with no round borders. Therefore 100% of the area of such a dataset is usable.

Morphology and coloring operations are applied over the CAD layers to obtain the RGB representation of the image. Slight distortions and Gaussian noise are also applied to the RGB image, in order to reflect the imperfections of the photo in the real setting.

The toy data implements 4 types of defect: dust, color anomalies representing nitride liftoff, residual resists and burned platinum on text. Samples of the 4 classes of defect are presented at

²The engine of the toy data generator is a tool that was implemented previously to this work. Our contribution is limited: We modified the tool to allow the use of real data, to include more variability to the added defects and to provide a controllable user interface.

Figure 4.8 A comparison between the 24 CAD layers for a real wafer (a) and the generated toy data (b).

Figure 4.9. The defect density for each kind of defect is a parameter of the generator program. The unit used is defects/Mpx – i.e. avg. amount of defects in a $1,000 \times 1,000$ pixel patch. For the case of burned platinum on text, the input parameter is the ratio of letters affected.

The dust defects, shown in Figure 4.9(a), are mimicked by randomly painting a pixel’s neighbourhood black. The size of the neighbourhood ranges from 1 to 5 pixels. The residual resists in Figure 4.10(b) are derived from 8 manually extracted defect samples. The samples had their background removed and are randomly selected, rotated, rescaled and sheared. The nitride liftoff shown in Figure 4.9(b) is simulated by random polygons, filled with the characteristic color for this kind of defect. Defects on text, such as the one in Figure 4.9(d), are modelled by randomly selecting a contour in the text layer and applying the darker shade of yellow associated with burned platinum.

Besides the flexibility in parametrization of defect density, the generated toy data also has pixel-perfect labels for the generated defects. This allows for a precise quantification of our methods with pixel-wise metrics. As also shown in Figure 4.1, the toy data generator generates RGB and binary images, which are then quantized and encapsulated in a single file by the “dataset generator” module.

4.5 Real data with artificial defects

We expand the mock data generation also to the real data, adding artificial defects to real data. We can parametrize the defect density of all classes in the same way as for the toy data, apart from the text, since the position of the text layer in the GDS data depends on the wafer series used. Another main difference from the toy data described above is that in the real data the defects are added over a previously quantized photo. This means that new colors that would be introduced by a certain defect might not be present in the palette and may end up wrongly represented. The defects added in the real data are shown in Figure 4.10.

Figure 4.9 We depict here the 4 defect classes implemented in the toy data: (a) dust particles, at 10000 defects/MPx; (b)nitride liftoff, at 100 defects/MPx; (c)residual resists or strange particles, at 100 defects/MPx; (d)burned platinum affecting 50% of the letters. The samples shown here were generated with a disproportionally high defect density when compared to real data, for increased visibility.

All defects are generated in the same way as for the toy dataset, then quantized to the palette from Figure 4.4(b) and added to the quantized photo. Due to the purple shade of the nitride liftoff not being in the palette, it appears as the closest possible color. The difference in hue doesn't change anything for the case of pixel-wise evaluation of the defect detection, as any anomalies should be detected by our method, but should be considered if used for augmenting data for training better simulators.

Figure 4.10 Appearance of artificial defects of different types added to real data: (a) dust particles, at 10,000 defects/MPx; (b) residual resists, at 100 defects/MPx; (c) nitride liftoff, at 100 defects/MPx. The samples shown here were generated with a disproportionally high defect density when compared to real data, for increased visibility.

5 Simulation: generation of a discretized synthetic image with a U-Net

Since we have a quantized target, we can frame the simulation problem as a per-pixel classification task, with a pixel $p_q(x, y) \in [1..64]$, for $k_{out} = 64$ colors of the computed palette. Due to the high correlation between structures in the input and output of the desired model, our setting can be described as a semantic segmentation problem. Due to noise in the target photo, misclassified samples can be tolerated to a certain degree, if there are ordinal relationships in the set of possible semantic labels.

Table 5.1 Similarity metrics between simulation from CAD layers to visual expression and the quantized photo. For reference, we list also results for different forms of simulation (decision tree and k -means clustering); to the untrained, randomly-initialized U-Net; and between the quantized photo and the raw RGB photo. Our method shows generally better quantitative results than the benchmarking samples. The results for the quantized photo show the best absolute values, which is expected, as it is not a simulation from the design layout.

	Simulation		Decision Tree		Untrained UNet		KMeans		Quant. Photo	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
L1 ↓	0.077	0.013	0.088	0.011	0.168	0.014	0.100	0.009	0.014	0.001
L2 ↓	0.023	0.008	0.028	0.007	0.055	0.010	0.023	0.006	0.000	0.000
PSNR ↑	19.314	0.853	17.704	0.703	13.774	0.548	18.202	0.621	34.721	0.378
SSIM ↑	0.616	0.025	0.536	0.020	0.396	0.021	0.515	0.022	0.954	0.003
LPIPS ↓	0.291	0.032	0.362	0.027	0.506	0.022	0.365	0.026	0.013	0.002
HaarPSI ↑	0.614	0.032	0.477	0.022	0.305	0.011	0.459	0.019	0.951	0.004
2-off Acc. ↑	0.536	0.023	0.462	0.017	0.156	0.013	–	–	–	–
Dice ↑	0.086	0.006	0.011	0.000	0.010	0.000	–	–	–	–
Cross entropy ↓	2.897	0.346	4.085	0.004	4.172	0.002	–	–	–	–
Focal loss ↓	2.785	0.332	4.065	0.004	4.152	0.002	–	–	–	–

We use a U-Net [62] and feed it with an image composed of k_{in} channels. In real data, $k_{in} = 24$, with each input layer corresponding to one of the 23 steps of the process, with one additional mask over the borders of the wafer. For toy data we use $k_{in} = 5$, as described in section 4.4. The network is then trained using the quantized photo of the wafer as a simulation target. The output of the U-Net has $k_{out} = 64$ channels, one for the confidence score s_s of each color in the defined quantized color-space. The quantized prediction is then

$$p_q(x, y) = \underset{c \in [1..k_{max}]}{\operatorname{argmax}} s_s(c, x, y) \quad (14)$$

and the RGB expression of the golden standard is given by the RGB valued indexed by p_q in the computed palette.

In training we use the batch-averaged categorical cross entropy as objective function and the ADAM optimizer [38], except where noted. We use a 0.001 initial learning rate, multiplied by a factor of 0.6 at end of epochs 1, 3, 5, and 8. Even though we train and validate a model over the same wafer, we partition the wafer first into a training and a validation part. This split is parametrized in the code as a ratio, so we can conduct experiments with several amounts of training data. The exact ratio and the amount of epochs vary by experiment.

In this chapter, we generate several similarity metrics to evaluate our simulation results. For some metrics we desire a higher score, which is indicated in the following results by the symbol of an arrow pointing up (↑). For metrics such as distances and loss functions, we aim at obtaining a lower score, and indicate accordingly (↓).

5.1 Learning performance

We evaluate our simulation performance after training on 50% of the wafer for only 5 epochs. Values shown are the mean across the batch averages. We used 128 samples per batch, with each sample having 128×128 pixels. We apply several of the discussed metrics to the output of the

model against either the RGB photo or the quantized target, where necessary. For comparison and context, we also applied the same metrics to the golden standards generated by a decision tree, k -means clustering and a randomly initialized U-Net. The decision tree is trained on the quantized photo, as it is a classification model. The k -means classifier converged to 64 centroids in the GDS input vector space. Each cluster was recolored with the average RGB value of the pixels corresponding to the positions assigned to that cluster in the photo. We also compare the RGB photo with the quantized photo, to provide a reference point of the range of scores that would indicate a near-perfect simulation. The averaged results over the whole validation section of the wafer – i.e. the half not used in training –, are seen on Table 5.1.

To provide more reference for the metrics shown, we select a few isolated patches with interesting properties. We compare the visual expression of the generated results with the local, patch-wise evaluation metrics for such predictions.

Figure 5.1 A background patch with a defect, and the reconstructions analysed in Table 5.2. All methods generate fairly smooth results, and the defect is absent from the simulations.

In Table 5.2 we see the results corresponding to the patch shown in Figure 5.1. It is mostly a pure background patch, with a defect. This type of patch is of interest as most of the wafer is composed of background. L1 and L2 norms are close to the other methods, but loss functions show a clear difference in score. This indicates that some metrics may be better at capturing the fundamental differences between approaches. When comparing the scores for this specific patch in the table against the global results on Table 5.1, we notice it shows higher similarity in all but one metric, confirming this is an easy kind of patch to learn.

More complex structures are shown in Figure 5.2 and Table 5.3. These experiments show how the model is capable of quickly learning complex structures, even if they are transparent. In fact, we can see in Figure 5.2 how even the untrained U-Net can already translate some structures from CAD-space to RGB.

We noticed that some smaller details are harder to learn. In particular, we analyse a patch with text. We can see how the metrics in Table 5.4 show a good result in regards to the benchmarks, although it is not perceptually good if we take into account the visual expression in Figure 5.3. In our simulation, the text looks relatively blurry, indicating that more training is needed for this kind of sample. At the same time, we notice that only our simulation shows the borders between the letters and the background. This structure is not present in the CAD data and highlights how our method successfully learns contextual information early in the training process.

The model trained on 5 epochs, as shown in Table 5.1, performs in average better than the benchmarks, but still has some deficiencies. It shows that for most of the wafer we can get good results with generally few training rounds. More detailed structures, such as text, don't get learned properly, which can be solved by training longer. A model trained for 100 epochs, for example, learns a better simulation. A comparison between text learned in 5 and 100 epochs is shown in

Table 5.2 Similarity metrics between simulation from CAD layers to visual expression of a patch containing purely background and a defect (shown in Figure 5.1). We list also results for the similarity of other references with the photo. Our method consistently outperforms the others presented.

	Simulation	Decision Tree	Untrained UNet	KMeans	Quant. Photo
L1 ↓	0.018	0.020	0.173	0.055	0.007
L2 ↓	0.001	0.001	0.043	0.003	0.000
PSNR ↑	32.370	31.264	13.647	24.732	41.033
SSIM ↑	0.889	0.815	0.782	0.812	0.956
LPIPS ↓	0.249	0.497	0.822	0.505	0.012
HaarPSI ↑	0.895	0.814	0.503	0.812	0.985
2-off Acc. ↑	0.557	0.551	0.002	–	–
Dice ↑	0.013	0.004	0.003	–	–
Cross entropy ↓	2.245	4.067	4.143	–	–
Focal loss ↓	2.165	4.046	4.123	–	–

Table 5.3 Similarity metrics between simulation from CAD layers to visual expression and the quantized photo, the patch shown in Figure 5.2, containing waveguides as most prominent structure. Our simulation outperforms all reference samples used.

	Simulation	Decision Tree	Untrained UNet	KMeans	Quant. Photo
L1 ↓	0.054	0.107	0.155	0.110	0.017
L2 ↓	0.011	0.026	0.053	0.021	0.001
PSNR ↑	24.087	15.865	12.748	16.824	32.991
SSIM ↑	0.788	0.491	0.074	0.442	0.974
LPIPS ↓	0.054	0.261	0.408	0.270	0.003
HaarPSI ↑	0.794	0.491	0.326	0.529	0.964
2-off Acc. ↑	0.415	0.313	0.199	–	–
Dice ↑	0.037	0.007	0.007	–	–
Cross entropy ↓	2.660	4.107	4.169	–	–
Focal loss ↓	2.580	4.086	4.149	–	–

Figure 5.4. We use the 100 epoch model for most applications and the defect detection evaluation presented later in this work.

We find that the trained model successfully learns faithful representation of the target wafer, and that the defect density in a production wafer is low enough for the models to properly simulate a golden standard, without learning the anomalous structures. We hypothesize that this is due to the direct correspondence of structures in the input data and the target photos. Those would allow the model to “underfit”, which in our case is desired. We also see from the results shown above that the CNN-based approach outperforms pixel-wise methods when there are contextual hints in the data.

5.2 Simulation robustness to increased defect density

We also train some models with artificially added defects of 3 types for several defect densities, to better understand the robustness of the simulation method against defect-density in the target

Figure 5.2 Simulation results for a patch with many detailed structures and transparent features. Metrics shown in Table 5.3. It is clear to see how our proposed simulation generates a result with more photo-realistic characteristics. In particular, we notice how the CNN correctly learns contextual structures, such as the darker traces around the copper tracks and the black contour of transparent components. The waveguides are transparent structures that need context from neighbouring pixels to be drawn correctly.

Figure 5.3 Simulation of a patch containing text with a model trained for 5 epochs, for which quantitative results are shown in Table 5.4. It is immediate to see that some smaller structures such as text are not learned properly. Perceptually, our simulation results are “blurry”, against legible and sharp letters generated by the other methods. The other methods do not simulate correctly the borders between letters and background, while this can be verified in our simulation.

photo. We train the models for 10 epochs each on 75% of the wafer image. Each batch contains 128 samples of size 64×64 pixels. The global results of this experiments are shown in Table 5.5, and samples predicted for each defect type and density are shown in figures 5.5 to 5.7.

Visual samples of the predictions can be seen in Figure 5.5 for dust, Figure 5.6 for residual resists and in Figure 5.7 for nitride liftoff. We find mostly that the defect density necessary to cause the models to learn how to hallucinate defects is unrealistically high, unlikely to be found in the real setting. We evaluate the models trained on artificial data using real data. Our results also indicate that different expressions of defects affect the simulator’s training process in different ways. We observe that that the computed performance scores for models trained with the “dust” kind of defect increase slightly for higher densities, indicating that this kind of defect could be used for some regularizing effect. This application is not obvious, as we observe in Table 5.5 that models trained on the other types of defects show better metrics, overall. Perceptually, we can say that in high densities the simulation quality in component areas deteriorates. Simulation of background areas seems to not suffer in any perceptible way for the range of dust defect-densities used in the

Table 5.4 Similarity metrics between simulation from CAD layers of a patch containing background and text to visual expression and the quantized photo. The results correspond to the patch shown in Figure 5.3. Using these metrics, our method outperforms all other reference patches.

	Simulation	Decision Tree	Untrained UNet	KMeans	Quant. Photo
L1 ↓	0.039	0.056	0.221	0.073	0.013
L2 ↓	0.005	0.008	0.066	0.009	0.000
PSNR ↑	25.706	21.024	11.772	20.658	35.213
SSIM ↑	0.704	0.440	0.341	0.433	0.958
LPIPS ↓	0.144	0.348	0.886	0.345	0.008
HaarPSI ↑	0.784	0.614	0.342	0.629	0.973
2-off Acc. ↑	0.481	0.448	0.000	–	–
Dice ↑	0.017	0.006	0.005	–	–
Cross entropy ↓	2.621	4.091	4.157	–	–
Focal loss ↓	2.547	4.071	4.137	–	–

Figure 5.4 Comparison of the predictions generated by a model trained for 5 epochs and a model trained for 100 epochs. At 5 epochs, some small detailed structures such as text are not well learned, even though most of the other features are well simulated, in perceptual terms. Training the model for longer improves the generated image.

Figure 5.5 Simulation results for models trained on real data with added defects of the *dust* type. The defect density of the training target is indicated under each sample. We observe that models don't immediately suffer from increased defect density. In fact, Table 5.5 indicates better simulation performances for 10^5 def./MPx. Perceptually, it is easy to see in (d) that extreme dust density decreases simulation performance in structures, but doesn't affect the learning of background.

Figure 5.6 Simulation results for models trained on real data with added *residual resists* defects. The defect density of the training target is indicated under each sample. For this kind of defect, simulation quality decreases monotonically as defect density in training target increases. The visual results on here reflect the full wafer metrics shown in Table 5.5.

experiment. Models trained on 10^2 defects/MPx of the nitride liftoff class behave mostly in the opposite way than the models trained on dust: complex structures and components are learned fairly well, while disrupting the learning of background areas. In fact, perceptual similarity metrics such as LPIPS and HaarPSI indicate better scores for this defect density than the others used. Simulation quality deteriorates if defect density is still increased. The effects of the added residual resists on training data, in the range used, impact negatively the computed metrics as their density increases. In the lower range, it is the defect type less likely to negatively affect prediction quality, if compared to the results obtained from the other classes.

We can conclude from this experiment that models successfully learn to predict golden standards of a wafer, even if relatively high defect densities are present in the target photo – i.e. from a particularly bad production batch. Above a certain defect density, which varies among each type of defect, models may learn how to hallucinate defects. In the experiments carried out by this work, this effect happens only for unrealistically high defect densities, not observed on the real data, indicating our simulation methodology is adequately robust for application.

Figure 5.7 Simulation results for models trained on real data with added defects mimicking *nitride liftoff*. The defect density of the training target is indicated under each sample. Increasing defect density in training target causes the model to focus on detailed structures up to a point, and decreases overall simulation performance for further increases. Full wafer metrics are in Table 5.5.

Table 5.5 Similarity metrics between simulation from CAD layers to visual expression and the quantized photo, for increased defect densities in the target photo. Metrics are computed using the original wafer’s photo as reference. The table also indicates for which metric we desire a higher score (\uparrow) and for which of the metrics we aim at obtaining a lower score (\downarrow). For reference, we list also results for different forms of simulation (decision tree and k -means clustering), to the untrained, randomly-initialized U-Net and between the quantized photo and the raw RGB photo. We train our simulation for 10 epochs, using 75% of the wafer as training data. We observe how some higher defect density – particularly in the form of dust, i.e. pepper noise –, can add some form of regularization to the learned model. Visual samples of the predictions can be seen in Figure 5.5 for dust, Figure 5.6 for residual resists and in Figure 5.7 for nitride liftoff. The regularization effect is not immediately apparent from the images alone.

Type of defect:	Dust				Residual Resists			Nitride Liftoff		
Defect density: (MPx ⁻¹)	10 ³	10 ⁴	10 ⁵	10 ⁶	10 ¹	10 ²	10 ³	10 ¹	10 ²	10 ³
L1 \downarrow	0.18	0.11	0.09	0.09	0.04	0.04	0.13	0.04	0.05	0.13
L2 \downarrow	0.09	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.01	0.04
PSNR \uparrow	20.63	22.37	23.90	23.68	28.70	27.16	21.61	25.03	25.74	20.95
SSIM \uparrow	0.50	0.57	0.59	0.57	0.63	0.63	0.53	0.63	0.62	0.54
LPIPS \downarrow	0.52	0.45	0.42	0.41	0.33	0.36	0.45	0.37	0.35	0.43
HaarPSI \uparrow	0.57	0.59	0.62	0.61	0.71	0.63	0.53	0.63	0.65	0.57
2-off Acc. \uparrow	0.43	0.51	0.54	0.53	0.59	0.62	0.43	0.59	0.56	0.40
Dice \uparrow	0.08	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.09	0.08	0.06	0.09	0.08	0.06
Cross entropy \downarrow	2.85	2.70	2.65	2.74	2.46	2.54	2.86	2.48	2.61	2.90
Focal loss \downarrow	2.75	2.57	2.54	2.64	2.35	2.43	2.78	2.38	2.51	2.83

5.3 Removal of low-variance patches

The simulation experiments shown above confirm that the models learn successfully with relatively few training iterations, and that intricate small structures are harder to learn. Due to the dataset composition, the model spends most of the training time being exposed to relatively simple patches – such as background regions, with a single color and no apparent structures. This causes redundant

learning of simple concepts and wastes compute. Therefore it is of our interest to limit the model’s exposure to structurally simple patches. We propose removing the simpler areas from the input data, filtering input patches by a variance threshold.

During training, we compute the patch-wise variance of the values in the quantized image before feeding a new sample to the model. Patches with variances below a user-defined threshold are dropped. For context, we show in Figure 5.8 some reconstructed samples and their corresponding variance in the quantized color-space. We observe in the samples that in fact the patches above a certain threshold show a balance of background and detailed structures. The effect doesn’t increase in any obvious way as we move to the higher-end of the variance range shown, which indicates that a different metric could be used.

Figure 5.8 Appearance of several patches over the corresponding variance in the discretized domain. Patches are recolored to the RGB space for this demonstration. We see that higher-variance patches also contain more complex structures, and that indeed background patches show lower variance values.

Nevertheless, we test our hypothesis by training simulators for one epoch for several variance thresholds. We train 10 simulators with cross-entropy loss, 0.01 initial learning rate and 128 64×64 pixel samples per batch for each of 4 variance thresholds and distinct random neural network parameter initializations. Before filtering for variance, the training set has 1,847,496 samples, and the validation set has 615,832 samples from an unseen portion of the same wafer. We compute the k -off accuracy ($k = 2$) of the prediction generated for the whole wafer, without thresholding for variance in inference. From tables 5.1 to 5.4 and accompanying figures, we know that 2-off accuracies above 0.5 indicate possibly good results.

In Figure 5.9 we can see how the removal of low-variance patches dramatically accelerates the training process, reducing the amount of samples needed to train a model which achieves the same 2-off accuracy. The figure also indicates that models in average reach an initial plateau before learning higher accuracy. The variability in the scatter plot shows that the trained model is also highly dependent in each model’s initialization, with some models reaching very high k -off accuracy after being exposed to less samples than others.

As the variance is maybe not the most informative metric for structural complexity, threshold values are to be chosen conservatively. By only feeding patches above a certain variance threshold to the model, we get a faster training, up to a point. We use a variance threshold of 100 for further experiments.

Figure 5.9 Achieved 2-off accuracy at several stages of the training process, for 5 different variance thresholds applied to the training samples. We train 10 models for each variance threshold, with different random initialization. Trendline is approximated across all runs by a polynomial regression with order 20, and confirms that models need less samples to learn if tif relative density of depicted structures increases vs background.

6 Defect detection and localization

The defect detection step in this work is unsupervised, in the sense that we only use the predictions generated by the simulator module compared against the actual photo we have. We aim to both detect and localize defects – i.e. identify whether some part of the image is a defect and be able to point out where the defect is located with regards to the whole image area. We perform defect detection and localization by measuring the similarity between the simulated golden standard and the original target photo. Our method follows the same general approach in template-matching-based defect detection as the general method outlined in Chapter 2:

- Computing some score map, which quantifies the differences between the golden standard and the photo.
- Applying a threshold to binarize the score map and achieve a binary classification map.

In general, both steps can be done in a myriad of ways. We compute the score map by applying the pixelwise cross-entropy function from Equation 1 to both objects. This is the same loss function used for training the network, but without averaging over the batch. It is interesting to note that, while we show the generated golden standards in RGB space, the similarity function actually takes as input the raw categorical prediction scores s_s and the target image in quantized space t_q .

We then evaluate the defect detection performance of our models in a threshold-free approach, to understand what might be the best value for the decision boundary. We discard bounding-box based evaluation in this step as a binarization threshold is needed to obtain the boxes. As mentioned in Chapter 4, most of our available ground-truth labels are much bigger than the defects, so pixelwise metrics are not accurate with this data.

Table 6.1 Characteristics of the data used for evaluating defect detection with pixel-wise metrics. We show the known defect density in the data used for training our evaluation models, and the LPIPS metrics of such trained models against both the clean datasets (i.e. R_1 and T_1) and the same dataset used in training – indicated in the first column. The toy data has $15,000^2$ pixels, and the datasets are indicated by T_k . Datasets coming from real data are called R_k , and contain some defects and labels besides the added defects. The defect density values shown in this table for the R_k datasets are for the added defects only. From the LPIPS scores, comparable to results in Chapter 5, we conclude that the models were adequately trained, and that the generated simulations are more similar to the clean data than to the data with higher defect density. Models were trained for 100 epochs.

Dataset	Defect density (def./MPx)			LPIPS (\downarrow)	
	Dust	Res. Resist	Liftoff	Clean	Self
T_1	0	0	0	–	0.25
T_2	1,000	5	5	0.25	0.29
T_3	10,000	50	50	0.33	0.45
R_1	0	0	0	–	0.51
R_2	1,000	5	5	0.52	0.54
R_3	10,000	50	50	0.44	0.53

To overcome those issues, we use the previously presented artificial data to generate artificial datasets on toy data and real data, and train simulator models on these datasets. Since we also generate well defined labels for artificial data, we can use pixel-wise, threshold-free metrics to evaluate our methods and to fine-tune parameters. Finally, we present some bounding-box based results for the real data.

6.1 Data & models used for pixelwise evaluation

We generate datasets with procedurally added defects both on toy data and on the real wafer. With the artificial data we have access to pixel-perfect label maps, which makes pixelwise evaluation possible. We generated the datasets with the defect densities listed in Table 6.1 and trained simulation models with them. The models were trained on 65% of the wafer, and the remaining 35% of the area was used for evaluating the simulation performance. Each training batch is composed by 64 samples of 64×64 pixels, and we train the models for 100 epochs.

To complement the metrics shown in Table 6.1, we also show samples of the golden standards generated by all models. The predictions generated by models trained on toy data (T_1 , T_2 and T_3) are shown in Figure 6.1. We also show sample predictions for the models trained on real data with added artificial defects (R_1 , R_2 and R_3) in Figure 6.2. When comparing the simulations generated for both kinds of data, we observe that models trained on T_3 and R_3 overfit to defects, due to the high defect density in the training data. The hallucinations observed on the samples shown and across the wafer do not correspond to the exact locations of the defects in the target photos, even for predictions from the area used for training. This indicates that the models are not overfitting to some particular structure in the input data, but learning to randomly generate defects.

The datasets described in this section were used to train the simulator models for the defect detection task, but will not be used for evaluation. For brevity, we will use the names R_k and

Figure 6.1 Recolored simulation samples for the models trained on artificial data.

Figure 6.2 Simulations from models trained on real data with added artificial defects.

T_k to designate the *models* trained on such data, with $k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$. To actually evaluate the defect detection performance, we generate still two validation datasets. Both for toy data and real data, we use a defect density of 8 def./Mpx for all classes of defects on this validation sets. The validation toy dataset has $10,000^2$ pixels. For the setting using real data, we add artificial defects to the same wafer used so far and remove the ground-truth labels. We do this in order to not skew our evaluation with excessive false positives in the labeled data.

6.2 Scoremap augmentation

The layers corresponding to the CAD layout might show some misalignment in relationship to the structures in the wafer’s photo. Many steps of our data processing pipeline can introduce systematic offsets, such as inaccuracies in the stitching of the several microscope photos that form the complete wafer photo, the imprecise choice of keypoints for alignment of GDS files to the photo and rounding errors when applying the homography transformation. Misalignment is most apparent near the border of structures containing horizontal or vertical lines.

The misalignment is an issue for defect detection, even though the models successfully learn a perceptually sufficient representation of a wafer’s appearance. In Figure 6.3(c) we can observe clearly the effect of such imperfections. Since our comparison function only compares raw scores across one pixel (such as the reconstruction methods used for benchmarking in Chapter 5), thin lines and other spatial detail show up strongly in the score map when applying the evaluation function to generated golden standard and photo.

We apply a similarity metric between a fixed point (x, y) in the quantized target t_q to several translations of the predicted scores s_s . The maximum translation is given by m , and we choose the minimum value among all the translations. Using the cross-entropy from Eq. 1, the process can be

Figure 6.3 Effect of scoremap augmentation for correcting misalignment issues. At a first glance, the photo (a) looks well-aligned to the obtained simulation (b). In (c) we can clearly see how horizontal lines with a slight misalignment receive a misleading high-score when applying the chosen pixel-wise similarity metric between the simulation raw scores and the quantized photo. We apply the augmentation strategy described here, and (d) shows how the min-polling of adjacent measures improves the generated score map, reducing the score for misaligned components and keeping the scores of defective samples largely unchanged. Samples produced by R_2 , an accurate simulation model trained on moderately high defect density. Used for detecting defects in the validation data, also with added artificial defects.

described by

$$s_{d,aug}(x, y) = \min_{i,j} (CE(s_s(x+i, y+j), t_q(x, y))), \quad (15)$$

where both i and $j \in [-m..m]$, and $s_{d,aug}$ is the resulting augmented score map. Any other pixel-wise similarity measure between predictions and target could also be used, but metrics for which a higher score are desired require max-pooling, instead.

One of these measures for a pair (i, j) will have a best-alignment of features, and thus a lower score. Choosing the minimum score among translations guarantees we are using the score of the best aligned version. Defects will generate higher scores for all translations, since they are not supposed to appear in the simulation and have no corresponding structure to be aligned to.

The effect of this measure is evident in the augmented score map shown in Figure 6.3(d). We also compare in Figure 6.4 the score distribution of the pixels labeled as defects or not, and it is clear how it improves separation of samples. We explore this measure’s effect on defect detection performance in the next section, in parallel to the performance of the standard score map.

6.3 Pixel-wise evaluation

We evaluate the defect detection capabilities of the models introduced in Section 6.1. We generate our defect detection score maps both with pixel-wise cross-entropy and with the augmented cross-entropy described above. For the augmented score map we use a translation offset from $m \in [-3..3]$ in both x and y axis. We evaluate the relationships between precision (PPV), recall (TPR) and specificity (FPR) at several thresholds.

We don’t provide pixel-wise plots for the whole wafers, as generating the results for this amount of data is computationally expensive for the scope of this project. On toy data, we evaluate the models using both data from regions unseen in training and regions that were used in training. The

Figure 6.4 Two histograms showing the amount of pixels in each score range, colored for class. The y -axis is clipped at 20,000, and actual maximum value in the clipped region reaches 131,549. We observe a greater separation in anomalies’ scores from regular samples after the augmentation is applied. Sample predicted by R_2 on the validation dataset, with translations in the range $\{-3..3\}$ both for x and y axis.

Figure 6.5 ROC for the T_k models, trained on toy data. All models perform better than chance, but models trained on higher defect density perform worse. At a first glance, scoremaps generated without augmentation provide a higher area under the curve, which is misleading when the data is heavily imbalanced.

results correspond to the area comprised by 12,800 patches with 128×128 pixels each. In real data, we evaluate our results in the portion of the dataset available for publication, which is inside the training region. From our simulation results and the robustness to overfit observed in the neural network, we consider that using training data for evaluation of the defect detection performance is not detrimental to the research aims of this thesis.

The ROC plots, depicted in Figure 6.5 for toy data and Figure 6.6 for real data, compare the standard and augmented classifiers obtained. The augmented score map exhibits a smaller area under the curve than the map generated by a pixel-wise similarity metric. This implies that, at the same True Positive Rate (TPR), the augmented classifier has a higher False Positive Rate (FPR) compared to the standard classifier. In other words, the augmented classifier tends to identify more good pixels as defects among all the negative samples, which may appear counter-intuitive initially. This behaviour is not surprising as it is well defined in literature [63, 14].

However, the discrepancy between the ROC curves and the precision-recall curves, as shown in Figure 6.7 for toy data and Figure 6.8 for real data, helps shed light on the situation. Upon closer

Figure 6.6 ROC for the R_k models, trained on real data with added artificial defects. All models perform better than chance. At a first glance, scoremaps generated without augmentation provide a higher area under the curve, which is misleading when the data is heavily imbalanced. In the ROC plot, defect density in training data seems to have little effect in defect detection performance.

Figure 6.7 AP for the T_k models, trained on toy data. For all models, the defect detection is increased when using the augmentation method introduced by this work. We have also a clear indication of the differences in performance from each model. T_1 , the model trained on clean data, has the better detection performance.

inspection, it becomes evident that the augmented score map outperforms the standard metric in terms of precision, which measures the rate of correct predictions among all the data predicted as positive. Despite the higher FPR, the augmented classifier manages to achieve a better precision for the same TPR, meaning it makes fewer incorrect predictions of good pixels as defects.

In figures 6.9 and 6.10, we plot specifically the precision (PPV), recall (TPR) and specificity (FPR) for a range of thresholds. When comparing, for example, the intersection of precision and recall for the model trained on T_1 in Figure 6.9, it is clear to see that there is a threshold for binarizing the augmented score map which provides a higher precision and higher recall while still keeping the false positive rate low. The key to understanding the seemingly contradictory impression from the plots shown before is that the FPR is in reality very low for low thresholds, due to the imbalance in our data. This finding highlights the importance of considering both ROC and precision-recall curves when evaluating classifiers, particularly in scenarios with limited positive samples and imbalanced class distributions.

The curves shown in this section indicate that the real datasets are less prone to effects from

Figure 6.8 AP for the R_k models, trained on real data with added artificial defects. For all models, the defect detection is increased when using the augmentation method introduced by this work. Models trained on data with less defects performing better. We have also a clear indication of the differences in performance from each model, when comparing to the ROC plots in Figure 6.6.

Figure 6.9 Binary classification metrics for defect detection on toy data, T_k . We show precision (orange), recall (blue) and specificity (green) for (a) the raw scoremap and (b) the augmented scoremap. We could use this plot to help us choose a binarization threshold, and it is clear to see that in the augmented setting there is a threshold where recall and precision are both high.

Figure 6.10 Binary classification metrics for defect detection on real data, R_k . We show precision (orange), recall (blue) and specificity (green) for (a) the raw scoremap and (b) the augmented scoremap. We could use this plot to help us choose a binarization threshold. In particular, we notice how the precision for R_1 is more stable in augmented case, and that both for R_2 and R_1 we get better trade-offs between precision and recall, as both curves intersect at a higher point

higher defect-density, up to a point, while toy data models trained on higher defect density show a more pronounced decrement in performance. We conclude that it is generally better to use a cleaner dataset to generate a better defect detection module for this pipeline.

6.4 Robustness grid search on toy data

To confirm some findings from the analysis shown above, we conduct a finer grained experiment to investigate the effect that the amount of data used for training and the defect density have on defect detection capabilities of our pipeline. In particular, we train 64 models on toy data for combinations of defect densities and training data amount. The defect density is increased linearly in 8 steps, starting at 0 defects/MPx up to a maximum of 300 defects/MPx, a value higher than the typical defect density found in the real data. The defect densities are increased the same way for all defect classes, except for the text defects, which are ignored. Models were also trained in 8 different sizes of datasets, for one epoch each. The dataset size started at 1 MPx and was increased linearly to 80 MPx. After training the models, the generated datasets are discarded: The results shown in this section are from the predictions generated by those models in the same validation dataset used in the pixel-wise evaluation of the previous sections.

For each model trained on each of the 8×8 settings, we compute both the average precision (the area under the precision-recall curve, or AUPRC) and the area under the ROC curve. Both metrics, shown in Figure 6.11 confirm our results from the previous section, namely the decrease in defect detection performance for increased defect density in the training data.

We also observe in the trend surface shown in Figure 6.11(b) that the average precision of the models tend to decrease once more data is used for training. This plot also shows, as in the section above, how the Precision-Recall curves are more informative than the ROC curve, as the same adverse effect to dataset size is not clearly observed in Figure 6.11(a).

We examine in particular two samples predicted by the models trained on lower defect density for two amounts of data. The samples are shown in figures 6.12(a) and 6.12(b). Figure 6.12(a) shows the prediction of a model trained on a 1000×1000 px patch, while the model from Figure 6.12(b) was trained on 80 such patches. It is clear to see that the model trained on more data tries to learn the noise in the background. We conclude it is not only possible to train a good simulation on a small amount of data, as it is actually desirable to do so. The learned noise is shown in detail in Figure 6.13.

More interestingly, we plot the score distribution of the score maps generated for each of the two models. The histograms relative to this data are shown in Figure 6.14, and the better separation provided by the model trained on less data is a strong indication that not only it is possible to train an adequate simulation model on a reduced amount of data, but it may also be desirable to do so, in the defect detection context.

6.5 Binarization & instance-based evaluation

In a fully automatic, instance-based application of the pipeline described by this thesis, it is of interest to provide bounding box detections of defects, a methodology which not only indicates if a pixel is part of a defect but aggregates many pixels which are part of the same instance of a given defect in a rectangular box.

We provide a tentative bounding box-based detector based on the score maps generated in the previous sections. We generate bounding boxes by binarizing a score map through a set threshold and extracting the contours of contiguous areas in this binarized map. The detailed list of coordinates which generate each contour are then reduced to only 4 points, defining a rectangular box

(a) AUROC in terms of both defect density and amount of training data.

(b) Average precision of several training configurations.

Figure 6.11 AUROC and average precision in terms of amount of training data and defect density. It is clear to see in (a) the AUROC plots how the defect density in the training data is detrimental for the defect detection. The (b) average precision values for the several training configurations confirms this trend and also indicates that training the models on more data may also influence negatively the defect detection performance.

(a) 1 MPx training set.

(b) 80 MPx training set.

Figure 6.12 Golden standard predictions trained on (a) 1 MPx and (b) datasets. The simulation model trained on more data approximates better the appearance of the photo, but overfits the background noise.

Figure 6.13 Detail of the background in Figure 6.12(b). The model trained on a 80 MPx dataset overfits to the noise, which is not desirable.

Figure 6.14 Histogram of the score distribution for defective pixels and good pixels, with no augmentations, for a model trained on (a) 1 MPx and (b) 80 MPx, on toy data. The model trained on more data has more difficulty in separating anomalies from regular pixels, presumably due to overfit.

Figure 6.15 mAP, AP01 and AP50. The plots were generated on a single 3000×3000 pixel sample for each of the datasets, using an offset interval $[-3 .. 3]$ for the scoremap augmentation.

which contains the set of points which describe the defect’s contours.

In instance-based defect detection, similarly as to pixel-wise binary classification, we encounter the challenge of striking a balance between high precision, aiming to detect all defects accurately, and low sensitivity, to reduce the number of false positives. To choose the best attainable threshold, we take a similar approach as the one used in the evaluation of the pixel-wise binary classification capability of the defect score map, and compute classification metrics for our validation data in a range of distinct thresholds.

Usually, object detection metrics discard predictions with IoU smaller than 0.5. In our case, as we have large labeled bounding boxes for small defects, we aim to consider any intersecting bounding boxes as a correct prediction. We compute the evaluation metrics used for COCO and Pascal VOC, with a modification in regards to the restrictive 0.5 IoU criterion. We introduce AP01, the average precision for all sets of predicted bounding boxes with an IoU $> 1\%$ in regards to the ground truth data. This generates the plots shown in Figure 6.15, which show significantly low scores and indicate a sub-optimal performance for our method in this setting.

From the plots in figures 6.9(a), 6.10(a), 6.10(a) and 6.15, we can observe in which interval the best binarization threshold might lie in, and also infer what margin of classification error we can achieve.

In Figure 6.16(a), we present the results of our analysis on the real dataset with intentionally introduced defects, trained on R_1 , utilizing insights from Figure 6.15(b) to set a threshold value of $T = 8$. The labeled data is highlighted in red, and a total of 90 defects are identified within this patch. The model’s detections are shown in green, yielding a total of 95 detections, out of which 68 are true positives, resulting in a TPR of 0.72%. Notably, the smallest Intersection over Union (IoU) value for a valid and correct prediction is 0.025%.

Moving on to the real data with hand-labeled ground-truth, Figure 6.16(b) displays the results of our analysis, where we employ a threshold value of $T = 7$, as it is determined to achieve the best average precision, as indicated by Figure 6.15(c). The red highlights in the figure correspond to the labeled data, containing a total of 18 defects in this patch. The model’s detections are presented in green, yielding 85 detections, out of which only 8 are true positives, resulting in a TPR of 0.09%. The smallest Intersection over Union (IoU) value found in this prediction is 2.1%.

An intriguing observation from both predictions shown in Figure 6.16 is the consistent presence of false positive detections near component borders or in the form of very small objects. This tendency of misclassifying borders, especially for horizontal and vertical lines, is attributed to the

(a) Bounding boxes captured on the validation dataset, with the binarization threshold set at $T = 8$.

(b) Bounding boxes captured on the original data, with the binarization threshold set at $T = 7$.

Figure 6.16 Bounding box detection.

effect demonstrated in Figure 6.3(c). The underlying cause of this effect lies in the misalignment of structures present in the CAD data, even when applying our scoremap augmentation strategy. This results highlights the fact that the misalignment issue in the input data propagates throughout the entire pipeline, significantly influencing the final detection results.

7 Results & discussion

In this work, we provided a pipeline for image-based defect detection on InP multi project wafers. A U-Net is trained to approximate the appearance of such a wafer from CAD layout data. We implement defect detection by computing the pixel-wise distance between the estimated result and the actual photo of the wafer.

The quality of the data used in the proposed pipeline plays a crucial role in both simulation and detection performance, and we acknowledge that higher resolution samples with less noise and a more complete set of detailed ground truth labels would be beneficial. Nevertheless, any data-related limitations are attributed to the data acquisition process rather than inherent flaws in the pipeline, and we expect a gain in performance with better data. Modifications to the data processing pipeline could also remove the processing steps that introduce misalignment. For example, we could use unstitched wafer photos mapped to positions in the CAD layout to remove the inaccuracies introduced by the stitching algorithm.

Notably, we find that the photo-realistic simulation of a golden standard wafer is readily achievable from the layout data, and modern computer vision and machine learning techniques enable rapid convergence of the training process to match the targets. We observe that the model used learns effortlessly the relationship between input and output data, and that such models don't learn directly the mechanisms behind the generation of anomalies in the process. It seems promising to apply similar methods to detect the effect on randomly-occurring disturbances in other processes where some desired output has a direct correlation with the input data. The identification of such application domains is left as future work.

Our results also indicate that the use of semantic segmentation models is adequate for learning

to approximate targets that contain noise, as seen in Figure 7.1. Such models show potential for application in domains where the target data can be described by a cyclic and ordered space – such as our chosen color palette. We propose the k -off accuracy measure, a step in the direction of the development of metrics which take those characteristics into account.

Figure 7.1 Prediction (left) and ground truth(right), where the ground truth doesn’t look like a traditional set of segmentation masks, but is instead affected by noise. The prediction on the other hand, has bigger contiguous areas of a same class/color, effect of the semantic segmentation model used. The misalignment between photo and prediction is also evident from this zoomed in sample, when looking at where the structures intersect with the image’s borders. The simulator was trained for 200 epochs with exposure to the whole wafer.

We posit that it is currently not possible to use the presented pipeline as a completely automated defect detection tool, as the binary classification of the obtained score maps incurs in an unsatisfactory trade-off of false detections for a good precision. This effect is clearly observable in the pipeline’s final output, a sample of which is shown in Figure 6.16. However, the unthresholded score map can be used in a “human-in-the-loop” system, as an enhancement tool for the manual quality control process. It is unlikely that a global threshold value will be the best binarization method, and some localized methods could be tested. Another interesting possible modification to the pipeline would be to use the score map as a segmentation label map for training a supervised defect detection model.

8 Conclusion

In this study we addressed the challenges of defect detection in experimental photonic InP MWP runs, an area which is a critical roadblock in the efficient development of new photonics-based technologies. This study is aimed on generating an artificial golden standard wafer image from the corresponding CAD layout data, and further investigating its use for template matching-based defect detection. We show that the simulation of this golden standard is easily attainable when framing the problem as a semantic segmentation problem. The use of a U-Net CNN architecture is adequate for the simulation task, and provides photo-realistic reconstructions of a defect-free wafer.

We also show that a pixel-wise similarity measure of the neural network’s prediction scores against the target photo can be used as a score map for unsupervised defect detection. The defect detection is limited in the sense that an optimal decision boundary is hard to be attained, in particular for small defects, due to noise in the data.

We list the following main contributions of our work:

- The implementation of the modular pipeline proposed, which has practical application value and can be used as a starting point for further work.
- The CNN-based golden standard generation methodology, and notions on its robustness against high defect density in training data.
- In defect detection, a very effective scoremap augmentation method, to alleviate issues arising from the inherent spatial misalignment on the kind of data used.
- The unexpected finding that the amount of data used for training is inversely proportional to the attained defect detection performance.

Our method’s automatic defect detection performance is limited, as predictions are very sensitive to noise in the score map and in the target photo. Noise in the image may show with higher amplitude than the deviation caused by some defects which cover the same area, and increasing the detection’s sensitivity for those small defects returns many false positives. The trade-off between high precision and high recall is a classic limitation in unsupervised binary classification, and not unexpected.

The pipeline we present in this work is fairly modular, composed of several chained methods which solve distinct tasks. For each processing step in this pipeline, we have identified multiple opportunities for improvement, which could serve as the foundation for several interesting research directions.

As is typical in the applied machine learning domain, we found that the available data for the development and evaluation of our methods is insufficient for a more rigorous evaluation. The high noise and low resolution in the images of the target wafer were also central to limit the total performance of the pipeline. We identify that better input data acquisition would be the most immediate way of continuing this work. We posit that higher resolution photos would increase the defects’ apparent size in relationship with the misclassified noise, immediately improving average precision for the correct threshold. To properly automate the method, a better binarization strategy for the score map is also needed. Additionally, a more precise evaluation of the methods shown will be possible only if there are comprehensively labeled defects to be used as trustworthy ground truth data.

Attaining an optimal binary classification from the generated score maps is still an open problem, but the unthresholded defect-score maps generated with the methods described in this work are still useful to indicate possible defect locations and problematic areas. In fact, the methods developed in this work are currently being actively used at HHI’s InP foundry, attesting their practical value.

Bibliography

- [1] Sertac Arisoy, Nasser M Nasrabadi, and Koray Kayabol. Unsupervised pixel-wise hyperspectral anomaly detection via autoencoding adversarial networks. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, 19:1–5, 2021.
- [2] Olatomiwa Badmos, Andreas Kopp, Timo Bernthaler, and Gerhard Schneider. Image-based defect detection in lithium-ion battery electrode using convolutional neural networks. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, 31(4):885–897, 2020.
- [3] Emrecan Bati, Akin Çalışkan, Alper Koz, and A Aydin Alatan. Hyperspectral anomaly detection method based on auto-encoder. In *Image and Signal Processing for Remote Sensing XXI*, volume 9643, pages 220–226. Spie, 2015.
- [4] Marylyn Hoy Bennett, Kenneth W Tobin Jr, and Shaun S Gleason. Automatic defect classification: status and industry trends. In *Integrated Circuit Metrology, Inspection, and Process Control IX*, volume 2439, pages 210–220. SPIE, 1995.
- [5] Paul Bergmann, Michael Fauser, David Sattlegger, and Carsten Steger. Mvtec ad—a comprehensive real-world dataset for unsupervised anomaly detection. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 9592–9600, 2019.
- [6] Prahar M Bhatt, Rishi K Malhan, Pradeep Rajendran, Brual C Shah, Shantanu Thakar, Yeo Jung Yoon, and Satyandra K Gupta. Image-based surface defect detection using deep learning: A review. *Journal of Computing and Information Science in Engineering*, 21(4), 2021.
- [7] Aleksei Boikov, Vladimir Payor, Roman Savelev, and Alexandr Kolesnikov. Synthetic data generation for steel defect detection and classification using deep learning. *Symmetry*, 13(7):1176, 2021.
- [8] Olivier Chapelle, Bernhard Scholkopf, and Alexander Zien. Semi-supervised learning. 2006. *Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press View Article*, 2, 2006.
- [9] Ssu-Han Chen, Chih-Hsiang Kang, and Der-Baau Perng. Detecting and measuring defects in wafer die using gan and yolov3. *Applied Sciences*, 10(23):8725, 2020.
- [10] Xiaoyan Chen, Jianyong Chen, Xiaoguang Han, Chundong Zhao, Dongyang Zhang, Kuifeng Zhu, and Yanjie Su. A light-weighted cnn model for wafer structural defect detection. *IEEE access*, 8:24006–24018, 2020.
- [11] Sejjune Cheon, Hankang Lee, Chang Ouk Kim, and Seok Hyung Lee. Convolutional neural network for wafer surface defect classification and the detection of unknown defect class. *IEEE Transactions on Semiconductor Manufacturing*, 32(2):163–170, 2019.
- [12] Roland T Chin and Charles A Harlow. Automated visual inspection: A survey. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, (6):557–573, 1982.
- [13] Paul B Chou, A Ravishankar Rao, Martin C Sturzenbecker, Frederick Y Wu, and Virginia H Brecher. Automatic defect classification for semiconductor manufacturing. *Machine vision and applications*, 9:201–214, 1997.

- [14] Jesse Davis and Mark Goadrich. The relationship between precision-recall and roc curves. In *Proceedings of the 23rd international conference on Machine learning*, pages 233–240, 2006.
- [15] Byron E Dom and Virginia Brecher. Recent advances in the automatic inspection of integrated circuits for pattern defects. *Machine Vision and Applications*, 8(1):5–19, 1995.
- [] Maximilian Dreyer, Reduan Achtibat, Thomas Wiegand, Wojciech Samek, and Sebastian Lapuschkin. Revealing hidden context bias in segmentation and object detection through concept-specific explanations. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 3828–3838, 2023.
- [16] Eran Eidinger, Roe Enbar, and Tal Hassner. Age and gender estimation of unfiltered faces. *IEEE Transactions on information forensics and security*, 9(12):2170–2179, 2014.
- [17] Jaume Escofet, Rafael Fonolla Navarro, Maria Sagrario Millan Garcia-Verela, and Josep Mallofre Pladellorens. Detection of local defects in textile webs using gabor filters. *Optical Engineering*, 37(8):2297–2307, 1998.
- [18] Mark Everingham, Luc Van Gool, Christopher KI Williams, John Winn, and Andrew Zisserman. The pascal visual object classes (voc) challenge. *International journal of computer vision*, 88(2):303–338, 2010.
- [19] Fernando A Fardo, Victor H Conforto, Francisco C de Oliveira, and Paulo S Rodrigues. A formal evaluation of psnr as quality measurement parameter for image segmentation algorithms. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1605.07116*, 2016.
- [20] JW Funck, Y Zhong, DA Butler, CC Brunner, and JB Forrer. Image segmentation algorithms applied to wood defect detection. *Computers and electronics in agriculture*, 41(1-3):157–179, 2003.
- [21] Santanu Ghorai, Anirban Mukherjee, M Gangadaran, and Pranab K Dutta. Automatic defect detection on hot-rolled flat steel products. *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, 62(3):612–621, 2012.
- [22] Qiandong Guo, Bing Zhang, Qiong Ran, Lianru Gao, Jun Li, and Antonio Plaza. Weighted-rxd and linear filter-based rxd: Improving background statistics estimation for anomaly detection in hyperspectral imagery. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, 7(6):2351–2366, 2014.
- [23] Junwei Han, Dingwen Zhang, Gong Cheng, Lei Guo, and Jinchang Ren. Object detection in optical remote sensing images based on weakly supervised learning and high-level feature learning. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 53(6):3325–3337, 2014.
- [24] Yu He, Kechen Song, Qinggang Meng, and Yunhui Yan. An end-to-end steel surface defect detection approach via fusing multiple hierarchical features. *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, 69(4):1493–1504, 2019.
- [25] Takashi Hiroi, Shunji Maeda, Hitoshi Kubota, Kenji Watanabe, and Yasuo Nakagawa. Precise visual inspection for lsi wafer patterns using subpixel image alignment. In *Proceedings of 1994 IEEE Workshop on Applications of Computer Vision*, pages 26–34. IEEE, 1994.

- [26] Weng Khuen Ho, A. Tay, Ying Zhou, and Kai Yang. In situ fault detection of wafer warpage in microlithography. *IEEE Transactions on Semiconductor Manufacturing*, 17(3):402–407, 2004. doi: 10.1109/TSM.2004.831536.
- [27] Alain Hore and Djemel Ziou. Image quality metrics: Psnr vs. ssim. In *2010 20th international conference on pattern recognition*, pages 2366–2369. IEEE, 2010.
- [28] Guanghua Hu, Junfeng Huang, Qinghui Wang, Jingrong Li, Zhijia Xu, and Xingbiao Huang. Unsupervised fabric defect detection based on a deep convolutional generative adversarial network. *Textile Research Journal*, 90(3-4):247–270, 2020.
- [29] Xiaodan Hu, Mohamed A Naiel, Alexander Wong, Mark Lamm, and Paul Fieguth. Runet: A robust unet architecture for image super-resolution. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops*, pages 0–0, 2019.
- [30] Gabriel Huang, Issam Laradji, David Vazquez, Simon Lacoste-Julien, and Pau Rodriguez. A survey of self-supervised and few-shot object detection. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2110.14711*, 2021.
- [31] Szu-Hao Huang and Ying-Cheng Pan. Automated visual inspection in the semiconductor industry: A survey. *Computers in industry*, 66:1–10, 2015.
- [32] Quan Huynh-Thu and Mohammed Ghanbari. Scope of validity of psnr in image/video quality assessment. *Electronics letters*, 44(13):800–801, 2008.
- [33] Kazunori Imoto, Tomohiro Nakai, Tsukasa Ike, Kosuke Haruki, and Yoshiyuki Sato. A cnn-based transfer learning method for defect classification in semiconductor manufacturing. In *2018 international symposium on semiconductor manufacturing (ISSM)*, pages 1–3. IEEE, 2018.
- [34] Phillip Isola, Jun-Yan Zhu, Tinghui Zhou, and Alexei A Efros. Image-to-image translation with conditional adversarial networks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 1125–1134, 2017.
- [35] Shruti Jadon. A survey of loss functions for semantic segmentation. In *2020 IEEE Conference on Computational Intelligence in Bioinformatics and Computational Biology (CIBCB)*, pages 1–7. IEEE, 2020.
- [36] Hyun-Koo Kim, Kook-Yeol Yoo, and Ho-Youl Jung. Color image generation from lidar reflection data by using selected connection unet. *Sensors*, 20(12):3387, 2020.
- [37] Tae San Kim, Jong Wook Lee, Won Kyung Lee, and So Young Sohn. Novel method for detection of mixed-type defect patterns in wafer maps based on a single shot detector algorithm. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, 33(6):1715–1724, 2022.
- [38] Diederik P Kingma and Jimmy Ba. Adam: A method for stochastic optimization. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1412.6980*, 2014.
- [39] Fred Kish, Vikrant Lal, Peter Evans, Scott W Corzine, Mehrdad Ziari, Tim Butrie, Mike Reffle, Huan-Shang Tsai, Andrew Dentai, Jacco Pleumeekers, et al. System-on-chip photonic integrated circuits. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Quantum Electronics*, 24(1):1–20, 2017.

- [40] Timo Kohlberger, Vivek Singh, Chris Alvino, Claus Bahlmann, and Leo Grady. Evaluating segmentation error without ground truth. In *Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention–MICCAI 2012: 15th International Conference, Nice, France, October 1-5, 2012, Proceedings, Part I 15*, pages 528–536. Springer, 2012.
- [41] Hyun Kum, Doeon Lee, Wei Kong, Hyunseok Kim, Yongmo Park, Yunjo Kim, Yongmin Baek, Sang-Hoon Bae, Kyusang Lee, and Jeehwan Kim. Epitaxial growth and layer-transfer techniques for heterogeneous integration of materials for electronic and photonic devices. *Nature Electronics*, 2(10):439–450, 2019.
- [42] Sangwook Lee. Color image-based defect detection method and steel bridge coating. In *Texas 47th ASC Annual International Conference Proceedings, Texas*, pages 1–7, 2011.
- [43] Hao Li, Zheng Xu, Gavin Taylor, Christoph Studer, and Tom Goldstein. Visualizing the loss landscape of neural nets. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1712.09913*, 2017.
- [44] Wei-Chen Li and Du-Ming Tsai. Wavelet-based defect detection in solar wafer images with inhomogeneous texture. *Pattern Recognition*, 45(2):742–756, 2012.
- [45] Dong Liang, Jiaying Pan, Yang Yu, and Huiyu Zhou. Concealed object segmentation in terahertz imaging via adversarial learning. *Optik*, 185:1104–1114, 2019.
- [46] Michael Liehr, Moritz Baier, Gloria Hoefler, Nicholas M Fahrenkopf, John Bowers, Richard Gladhill, Peter O’Brien, Erman Timurdogan, Zhan Su, and Fred Kish. Foundry capabilities for photonic integrated circuits. In *Optical Fiber Telecommunications VII*, pages 143–193. Elsevier, 2020.
- [47] Tsung-Yi Lin, Michael Maire, Serge J. Belongie, Lubomir D. Bourdev, Ross B. Girshick, James Hays, Pietro Perona, Deva Ramanan, Piotr Dollár, and C. Lawrence Zitnick. Microsoft COCO: common objects in context. *CoRR*, abs/1405.0312, 2014. URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1405.0312>.
- [48] Tsung-Yi Lin, Priya Goyal, Ross Girshick, Kaiming He, and Piotr Dollár. Focal loss for dense object detection. In *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision*, pages 2980–2988, 2017.
- [49] Li Liu, Wanli Ouyang, Xiaogang Wang, Paul Fieguth, Jie Chen, Xinwang Liu, and Matti Pietikäinen. Deep learning for generic object detection: A survey. *International journal of computer vision*, 128(2):261–318, 2020.
- [50] Chi-Jie Lu and Du-Ming Tsai. Independent component analysis-based defect detection in patterned liquid crystal display surfaces. *Image and Vision Computing*, 26(7):955–970, 2008.
- [51] PM Mahajan, SR Kolhe, and PM Patil. A review of automatic fabric defect detection techniques. *Advances in Computational Research*, 1(2):18–29, 2009.
- [52] Abdul Mujeeb, Wenting Dai, Marius Erdt, and Alexei Sourin. Unsupervised surface defect detection using deep autoencoders and data augmentation. In *2018 International Conference on Cyberworlds (CW)*, pages 391–398. IEEE, 2018.
- [53] Nirbhar Neogi, Dusmanta K Mohanta, and Pranab K Dutta. Defect detection of steel surfaces with global adaptive percentile thresholding of gradient image. *Journal of the Institution of Engineers (india): Series B*, 98(6):557–565, 2017.

- [54] Jim Nilsson and Tomas Akenine-Möller. Understanding ssim. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2006.13846*, 2020.
- [55] Robert Thomas Olszewski. *Generalized feature extraction for structural pattern recognition in time-series data*. Carnegie Mellon University, 2001.
- [56] DI Oni, JA Ojo, BO Alabi, AA Adebayo, and AE Amoran. Patterned fabric defect detection and classification (fddc) techniques: a review. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 9(2):1156–1165, 2018.
- [57] Maxime Oquab, Léon Bottou, Ivan Laptev, and Josef Sivic. Is object localization for free?-weakly-supervised learning with convolutional neural networks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 685–694, 2015.
- [58] Rafael Padilla, Wesley L Passos, Thadeu LB Dias, Sergio L Netto, and Eduardo AB da Silva. A comparative analysis of object detection metrics with a companion open-source toolkit. *Electronics*, 10(3):279, 2021.
- [59] Junting Pan, Chengyu Wang, Xu Jia, Jing Shao, Lu Sheng, Junjie Yan, and Xiaogang Wang. Video generation from single semantic label map. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 3733–3742, 2019.
- [60] Joseph Redmon and Ali Farhadi. Yolov3: An incremental improvement. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1804.02767*, 2018.
- [61] Rafael Reisenhofer, Sebastian Bosse, Gitta Kutyniok, and Thomas Wiegand. A haar wavelet-based perceptual similarity index for image quality assessment. *Signal Processing: Image Communication*, 61:33–43, 2018.
- [62] Olaf Ronneberger, Philipp Fischer, and Thomas Brox. U-net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation, 2015.
- [63] Takaya Saito and Marc Rehmsmeier. The precision-recall plot is more informative than the roc plot when evaluating binary classifiers on imbalanced datasets. *PloS one*, 10(3):e0118432, 2015.
- [64] Abhinav Shrivastava, Abhinav Gupta, and Ross Girshick. Training region-based object detectors with online hard example mining. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 761–769, 2016.
- [65] Pawan Sinha and Richard Russell. A perceptually based comparison of image similarity metrics. *Perception*, 40(11):1269–1281, 2011.
- [66] Meint Smit, Xaveer Leijtens, Huub Ambrosius, Erwin Bente, Jos Van der Tol, Barry Smalbrugge, Tjibbe De Vries, Erik-Jan Geluk, Jeroen Bolk, Rene Van Veldhoven, et al. An introduction to inp-based generic integration technology. *Semiconductor Science and Technology*, 29(8):083001, 2014.
- [67] Meint Smit, Kevin Williams, and Jos Van Der Tol. Past, present, and future of inp-based photonic integration. *APL Photonics*, 4(5):050901, 2019.

- [68] Carole H Sudre, Wenqi Li, Tom Vercauteren, Sebastien Ourselin, and M Jorge Cardoso. Generalised dice overlap as a deep learning loss function for highly unbalanced segmentations. In *Deep Learning in Medical Image Analysis and Multimodal Learning for Clinical Decision Support: Third International Workshop, DLMIA 2017, and 7th International Workshop, ML-CDS 2017, Held in Conjunction with MICCAI 2017, Québec City, QC, Canada, September 14, Proceedings 3*, pages 240–248. Springer, 2017.
- [69] Domen Tabernik, Samo Šela, Jure Skvarč, and Danijel Skočaj. Segmentation-based deep-learning approach for surface-defect detection. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, 31(3): 759–776, 2020.
- [70] Ye Tao, Petar Palasek, Zhihao Ling, and Ioannis Patras. Background modelling based on generative unet. In *2017 14th IEEE International Conference on Advanced Video and Signal Based Surveillance (AVSS)*, pages 1–6. IEEE, 2017.
- [71] Du-Ming Tsai and Ron-Hwa Yang. An eigenvalue-based similarity measure and its application in defect detection. *Image and Vision Computing*, 23(12):1094–1101, 2005.
- [72] Ihar Volkau, Abdul Mujeeb, Dai Wenting, Erdt Marius, and Sourin Alexei. Detection defect in printed circuit boards using unsupervised feature extraction upon transfer learning. In *2019 International Conference on Cyberworlds (CW)*, pages 101–108. IEEE, 2019.
- [73] Ting-Chun Wang, Ming-Yu Liu, Jun-Yan Zhu, Andrew Tao, Jan Kautz, and Bryan Catanzaro. High-resolution image synthesis and semantic manipulation with conditional gans. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 8798–8807, 2018.
- [74] Xinyu Wang, Xiaoli Jia, Chuyi Jiang, and Sanxin Jiang. A wafer surface defect detection method built on generic object detection network. *Digital Signal Processing*, page 103718, 2022.
- [75] Xianghua Xie. A review of recent advances in surface defect detection using texture analysis techniques. *ELCVIA: electronic letters on computer vision and image analysis*, pages 1–22, 2008.
- [76] Fan Yang, Mengnan Du, and Xia Hu. Evaluating explanation without ground truth in interpretable machine learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.06831*, 2019.
- [77] Dingwen Zhang, Junwei Han, Gong Cheng, and Ming-Hsuan Yang. Weakly supervised object localization and detection: A survey. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 44(9):5866–5885, 2021.
- [78] Jiun-Ming Zhang, Ruey-Ming Lin, and Mao-Jiun J Wang. The development of an automatic post-sawing inspection system using computer vision techniques. *Computers in Industry*, 40(1):51–60, 1999.
- [79] Kai Zhang, Shuhang Gu, and Radu Timofte. Ntire 2020 challenge on perceptual extreme super-resolution: Methods and results. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops*, pages 492–493, 2020.
- [80] Richard Zhang, Phillip Isola, Alexei A Efros, Eli Shechtman, and Oliver Wang. The unreasonable effectiveness of deep features as a perceptual metric. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 586–595, 2018.

- [81] Zhengxia Zou, Zhenwei Shi, Yuhong Guo, and Jieping Ye. Object detection in 20 years: A survey. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1905.05055*, 2019.